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Impact of Elicitation Techniques on Requirement Validation in Software Industry in Pakistan

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Abstract- In Requirement Engineering (RE), requirements are collected and formalized from all the stakeholders using various elicitation techniques. Afterwards, these requirements are validated at the validation phase before the actual design and development phases can initiate. At the validation stage of RE, requirement specifications are tailored to ensure that the requirements are correct, consistent, complete, and unambiguous. To achieve these objectives, the RE team should select the most suitable elicitation technique during the RE elicitation process. In Pakistan software industry, these techniques include interviews, prototyping, questionnaires, and observations. From literature, it is observed that most of the IT firms do not hire specialized RE teams for requirement gathering; instead, the requirements are collected mostly by the development team. Therefore, the primary motivation of this article is to provide a guideline for IT firms and software industry in Pakistan to select the right type of elicitation techniques for requirement gathering. This article presents the results of a comprehensive survey to evaluate the impact of elicitation techniques on requirement validation process in Pakistan software industry. We distributed a questionnaire to several IT firms across the country, and collected important data corresponding to their procedures of requirement gathering. We focused on the individuals responsible for RE processes, and our main conclusion is that requirements are mostly gathered by developers rather than specialized RE teams. Our results also show that prototyping is the most effective elicitation technique for mobile development, whereas interviews are preferred in case of Web & Desktop applications.

Keywords- Requirement Engineering (RE), SDLC, Elicitation Techniques, Requirement Validation, IT Industry in Pakistan

I. INTRODUCTION

Requirement Engineering (RE) is a fundamentally significant and immensely complicated stage in the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC). A requirement engineer should have an in-depth knowledge and skill corresponding to all the processes and activities performed during the RE phase [1]. For a software developing process, the most complicated issue is the accurate identification of all the modules and interfaces of the product being build. For this purpose, the role of a requirement engineer is to consult the user in order to gather all the relevant product information to satisfy the customer needs [2][3]. As a first step of RE, the customer's needs and understanding of the problem to resolve are formulated; this step is known as requirement elicitation [4][5]. There are several elicitation techniques utilized for software product development, but applying suitable technique for a particular project is the key to its successful completion. The selection of the most appropriate elicitation technique depends on various factors such as, project budgets, deadlines, type of development, business measures, personal choices, and development tools etc. [6][7]. Based on the right technique, the system analysts can develop a viable strategy to encompass all the aspects of the development which include the interfaces, tools, timelines, goals, and management related issues. Subsequently, a document based on these requirements is generated. The system

development team can then utilize this document to build modules and their interfaces, and integrate the modules into the overall system according to customer's needs [4][8]. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to understand and document the requirements during the elicitation stage to avoid incorrect, inconsistent and ambiguous results [9][10]. Hence the user requirements should be documented in an absolutely consistent, clear, and complete manner thereby following strict procedures to make sure that all the stakeholders are satisfied [13][14]. Therefore, the requirement validation process is invoked to ensure the authenticity of user's requirement during the elicitation stage to eradicate any possible inconsistency before the design and development stages [11][12].

In recent years, Pakistan has witnessed an exponential growth in software development industry [28]. More particularly, numerous freelance developers as well as IT firms are developing applications ranging from mobile apps for Google, Apple, and Microsoft Play Stores to web and desktop applications for foreign companies which outsource their projects to low-cost countries. In this scenario, it is extremely important to guide these developers to use the right elicitation techniques before the initiating the development of their products. The primary motive of this research study is to analyze the impact of a particular elicitation technique on requirement validation for different software projects in Pakistan. Therefore in this paper, we present a comprehensive survey to evaluate various elicitation techniques used in Pakistan software industries in terms of requirement validation criteria, i.e., ambiguity, consistency, completeness, and correctness. We collect online data of different software industries and circulate a questionnaire to them across the country. We focused on individuals who are responsible for gathering requirements for software development regardless of their positions in their firms. We discovered that oftentimes, the requirements are gathered from users by the software developers who play an additional role of requirement engineers too. To the best of our knowledge, no previous study has compiled evaluated elicitation techniques in RE in software industry in Pakistan. Our study provides two significant results: a) For Mobile apps development, the most effective elicitation technique is prototyping, and b) for Web & Desktop applications, interviews are considered as the best elicitation technique.

The rest of the paper is divided into the following sections. In Section 2, we present a thorough literature review on RE and elicitation techniques. We also discuss a theoretical framework of elicitation techniques in software industry. Section 3 provides our methodology to conduct this research study in terms of various steps from problem identification to data analysis. In Section 4, we discuss the results of this study. Finally, the paper is concluded in Section 5 along with some future directions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Requirement Engineering (RE)*

The IT industry is growing rapidly in the developing world due to the availability of low-cost workforce which acquires projects outsourced from the advanced countries. In Pakistan, various IT firms and freelancing groups are producing quality software, but they have potential to expand in future at exponential rates [15][16][28]. Therefore, proper usage of established processes like Requirement engineering (RE) can play a significant role for successful development of their projects in order to further their growth. Unfortunately in software industry in Pakistan, RE practices are either overlooked or performed by developers instead of requirement engineers [1][17][18]. During the RE process, there are four phases namely, i) Requirement Elicitation, ii) Requirement Analysis, iii) Requirement

Specification, and iv) Requirement Validation [19]. In this study, we focus on elicitation phase in terms of IT projects validation to ascertain the effectiveness of elicitation techniques used at an early RE stage.

B. Issues in Requirement Engineering

In software industry in Pakistan, most of the project failures are attributed to the poor perception of the RE among various stakeholders like developers, requirement engineers, customers, and IT managers [2]. Using appropriate RE techniques is of paramount importance, but they are usually avoided due to their tremendous costs, time constraints, and unprofessional practices such as, poor requirement gathering, documentation, management, and validation [2][20][21]. In addition to these factors, in Pakistan particularly, the most common issues are reported as poor coordination, ambiguities related to the natural languages, lack of field knowledge, lack of will, poor analysis, cultural differences, and weak skills [22][23].

C. Requirement Elicitation Techniques

According to [6], the requirement elicitation techniques used in IT industry in Pakistan are primarily questionnaires, prototyping, interviews, and observation. Figure. 1 presents the percentage of each type of technique used in Pakistan [6]. It is observed that stakeholders in Pakistan IT industry prefer to use interviews for requirement gathering [6][24].

Figure 1. Requirement elicitation techniques used in Pakistan’s software industries [6].

Various IT firms and software enterprises work to develop a variety of projects in different application areas, and depending on the customer’s needs and nature of a project, the requirement engineers opt for the best possible elicitation technique which ensures to gather complete, consistent, correct, and unambiguous requirements from the customers [25]. In order to achieve these objectives, the requirement engineer should be able to select the right elicitation techniques, because RE elicitation provides the foundation for any project. An improper elicitation technique may lead to an incomplete project or even a totally failed project [3].

C. Theoretical Framework

Figure. 2 depicts the theoretical framework of the requirement elicitation techniques in software development industry. In the first phase, the software application to be elicited is selected and analyzed from the RE perspective.

In the next phase, the most suitable requirement elicitation technique is selected for the given application. Finally, after applying the technique, requirement parameters are checked on the basis of validation criteria.

Figure 2. Theoretical framework of the requirement elicitation process in the software industry [27]

III. METHODOLOGY

Our study is empirical in nature and the scope of the study covers projects like mobile, web and desktop applications. The unit of analysis was project managers, team leaders, requirement engineers, and developers to target those personal who are gathering requirements for developing software regardless of their position in their firm or organization. More specifically, we have conducted a survey to ascertain each requirement elicitation technique used in Pakistan software industries in terms of the standard validation parameters such as, correctness, consistency, unambiguous, and completeness. For this a Questionnaire was developed with many Multiple Choice Questions (MCQs) using the Google forms portal. We collected data of different software industries from their websites in Pakistan and circulated the Questionnaire in these industries located across the country.

Figure 3. Research Methodology [27]

The data collected from the Questionnaires from all the respondents was presented on the 3-point Likert scaling (1 = High, 2 = Normal, 3 = Low). The acquired scale exhibited very good reliability, because the Cronbach’s Alpha values settled on the scale of high reliability i.e. between 0.83 and 0.90 [26][27]. Figure. 3 presents the various steps taken during this research work. First, we identified the problem and analyzed it through literature survey and floated questionnaires among all the stakeholders in the software industry. Subsequently, we collected the data from the responses and analyzed it.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of 215 questionnaires were circulated in various software firms using the Google Forms to collect the desired data. Out of those 215, we received 143 responses, thereby leading to a response rate of 66.5%. The 143 respondents were further categorized into three types: the mobile developers (62), the web applications developers (50), and the desktop application developers (31).

A. Organizational Profile

From the responses, we concluded that requirement elicitation in almost all software firms is normally performed by the software developers. Figure. 4 presents a breakdown of the personnel in various software firms who perform the elicitation process. It is evident that, of 55% (or 78 individuals) of the total occasions, elicitation is performed by the developers, whereas the requirement engineers perform it only 13.3% of occasions. On other occasions, testers (9.8%) and project managers (22.4%) perform the requirement elicitation tasks.

Figure 4. Participants Profile

B. Organizational Size

Figure. 5 presents the sizes of the organizations which participated in our study. It is clear from the figure that the majority of these organizations are of small (<10 employees) or medium (between 10 & 49 employees) sizes. Only 16 organizations confirmed that their employees’ strength is more than 50 personnel. In addition, the education levels of the participants were at least bachelor degree or more: 77.6% had BS degree(s) and 22.4% had M Phil/MS degree(s).

Figure 5. The size of organizations participated in the survey for the study

C. Dedicated Requirement Engineering Team

From the below results, we have concluded that the majority of software industries in Pakistan lack a dedicated RE team, which pose a big problem for project completion at different stages. Most of these organizations depend on a random member of their development team without relying on a qualified RE team. Consequently, this emerges as a big challenge for the industry and ensues in incomplete or incorrect requirements gathering. From Figure. 6, it is clear that only 20% of the respondents confirmed to have a dedicated RE team, while the other 80% organizations do not have dedicated teams, and hence they rely on individuals for requirements gathering.

Figure 6. Only 20% of the respondents indicated that their organization has dedicated RE teams

D. Professional Experience

Figure. 7 depicts the working experience of various participants in their field. It can be observed that a sizeable majority of participants have experience of five years or less. A total of 29 respondents (or 20%) confirmed that their work experience is between 1 & 2 years, whereas 41 (or 29%) responded with work experience of 3 to 5 years.

Similarly, 58 participants indicated that they have work experience in software industry between 6 to 9 years. Only 15 individuals confirmed that they have experience of more than 10 years in this field.

Figure 7. Professional Experience of various participants in the survey

E. Validation Criteria

A software developer expects absolutely clear, correct, complete, consistent, and unambiguous requirements. An RE team should be able to formalize the requirements to specify the details of all modules to be developed. Furthermore, it should ensure that the specifications are detailed enough to proceed to the advanced stages of the development process. Table 1 presents various results of our survey in terms of validation criteria of completeness, correctness, consistency, and unambiguous requirements for three different classes of applications: Mobile, Web, and Desktop applications.

TABLE I: EVALUATION OF REQUIREMENT ELICITATION TECHNIQUES FOR RE VALIDATION CRITERIA FOR MOBILE APPLICATIONS DEVELOPED IN PAKISTAN SOFTWARE INDUSTRIES

Mobile Application												
Requirement Validation Criteria	Prototyping			Interview			Questionnaire			Observation		
	High	Normal	Low	High	Normal	Low	High	Normal	Low	High	Normal	Low
Completeness	88%	7%	5%	70%	22%	8%	40%	28%	32%	18%	10%	72%
Consistency	91%	3%	6%	75%	16%	9%	36%	40%	24%	10%	43%	47%
Correctness	79%	10%	11%	76%	18%	6%	40%	27%	33%	23%	39%	38%
Unambiguous Requirement	85%	12%	3%	86%	6%	8%	29%	33%	38%	12%	32%	56%

From Table I, it is evident that the participants preferred to utilize the prototyping technique if they are looking to develop mobile applications. The respondents suggested that in order to obtain correct, unambiguous, complete, and consistent requirements, prototyping is the most suitable elicitation technique to acquire the requirements. Their second most preferred option is interviewing to get the requirements, followed by questionnaires and observations.

TABLE II: EVALUATION OF REQUIREMENT ELICITATION TECHNIQUES FOR RE VALIDATION CRITERIA FOR WEB APPLICATIONS DEVELOPED IN PAKISTAN SOFTWARE INDUSTRIES

Mobile Application												
Requirement Validation Criteria	Prototyping			Interview			Questionnaire			Observation		
	High	Normal	Low	High	Normal	Low	High	Normal	Low	High	Normal	Low
Completeness	81%	5%	14%	86%	6%	8%	40%	38%	22%	23%	13%	64%
Consistency	75%	14%	11%	85%	7%	8%	31%	45%	24%	27%	23%	50%
Correctness	60%	22%	18%	72%	19%	9%	37%	23%	40%	18%	21%	61%
Unambiguous Requirement	56%	39%	5%	68%	10%	22%	29%	46%	25%	35%	19%	46%

TABLE III: EVALUATION OF REQUIREMENT ELICITATION TECHNIQUES FOR RE VALIDATION CRITERIA FOR DESKTOP APPLICATIONS DEVELOPED IN PAKISTAN SOFTWARE INDUSTRIES

Mobile Application												
Requirement Validation Criteria	Prototyping			Interview			Questionnaire			Observation		
	High	Normal	Low	High	Normal	Low	High	Normal	Low	High	Normal	Low
Completeness	61%	20%	19%	73%	19%	8%	28%	26%	46%	23%	14%	63%
Consistency	72%	17%	11%	78%	12%	10%	36%	19%	45%	12%	32%	56%
Correctness	64%	23%	13%	81%	10%	9%	31%	31%	38%	33%	19%	48%
Unambiguous Requirement	70%	19%	11%	74%	14%	12%	27%	25%	48%	17%	21%	62%

For Web & Desktop applications, the respondents preferred to utilize the option of interviewing the user as shown in Table II and III. Subsequently, they prefer prototyping as their second best option, followed by observation and questionnaires. Therefore, in order to get correct, complete, unambiguous, and consistent requirements for their Web & Desktop applications before development, the industry prefers to take interviews of their customers and other stakeholders. The results presented can play a vital role in the development of professional procedures, proper documentation process, and clarity before development in various IT firms, freelance individual developers, and the overall public/private software industry.

III. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we presented the results of our survey in order to observe the processes of Pakistan’s software industry to gather requirements using various elicitation techniques. For better and accurate results, the sample size of the population (i.e., IT firms) that is participating in the survey should be more representative of various organizations and a larger portion of the stakeholders [9]. Our sample size is medium, but it is still reasonable considering the recently-growing software industry in Pakistan. Therefore, our results give an insight into the requirement elicitation methods used in Pakistan. From the published SDLC literature, we reckoned that the most common software practices are prototyping, interviewing, observation, and questionnaires. From our results, we observed that IT firms do not hire dedicated engineers for requirement gathering. More specifically, our study indicates that only 20% of the software firms have hired dedicated RE teams.

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TRAINING AN INTELLIGENT TUTORING SYSTEM USING REINFORCEMENT LEARNING

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Abstract: In this work we have applied reinforcement learning in building an intelligent tutoring system. An intelligent tutoring system is a computer system that provides personalized learning material to the learner, based on his needs and level of knowledge. Such a system may consist of the following components: the knowledge base, the student's model, the pedagogical module and the user interface. The role of the pedagogical module is to define what is the best learning material to give to the students in order to help them reach their goal towards learning the material of the course. This is a continuation of our previous work that models an intelligent tutoring system as a reinforcement learning problem for teaching different lessons related to Python programming language [1]. In this work, we focus on building the pedagogical module through applying reinforcement learning and the DQN algorithm. To model a problem as a reinforcement learning problem, we should take special care in defining the following components: the state space, the actions and the rewards. Here, we propose a way to organize the state space, the actions and the rewards, in order to train the pedagogical module using reinforcement learning. After defining those elements, we train this module using different parameters and conditions. The training is done in a simulated environment, by simulating the behavior of the student in order to help the training process.

Keywords: intelligent tutoring system, reinforcement learning, DQN

1. INTRODUCTION

An overview on intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) is given in our previous study [1]. According to that, an ITS is a system that adapts to every student based on factors such as pre-existing knowledge, learning style and student progress, by making personalized decisions for everyone. In this way, the ITS can customize the learning experience that the students perceive. Principles of artificial intelligence may be applied in the design of such systems in order to make them more intelligent and we focus on applying reinforcement learning for doing so. This class of machine learning algorithms has been applied in different approaches for designing ITS such as in the works from [2], [3], [5], [6], [7], [8].

Here, we extend our previous work for modeling an ITS by focusing on the knowledge factor [1]. The student starts learning the course materials and may or may not have some previous knowledge of the concepts that this course teaches. Each lesson of the course teaches some concepts, and we define an order for the lessons that are to be taught. We assume that the student cannot continue to the next lesson if he/she has not learned all the concepts that are presented in the current lesson. So, it is the duty of the pedagogical module to decide what learning material to give to the student, by determining if he/she should still stay in the current lesson or go to the next one. We model this module using reinforcement learning and then train it to learn what are the best actions to take to help the student learn the course material.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: in section 2 we describe the proposed model, in section 3 we describe the simulation that we have done, in section 4 we detail the experiments and the results and in section 5 give the conclusions of our work.

2. PROPOSED MODEL

The model that we propose here is a continuation of our previous work. As explained in [1], the learning material is organized in lessons, where each lesson teaches some new concepts and requires some prior concepts to be known by the student. Here, we have added another relation between the lessons where for each lesson we define what is the next lesson to go. In this way, we create a sequence of lessons that the student must follow in order to complete the learning path. The relation between lessons and concepts is given detailed in Figure 1. The idea presented here is slightly different from the one given in our previous work: before starting the course, the student may or may not have previous knowledge of the concepts that the course teaches; the student starts always from the first lesson; the system should make sure that the student learns all the concepts that are presented in the current lesson before going to the next one.

Lesson	Required concept	New concept learned	Next lesson
Introduction	None	1. Introduction	Variables and types
Variables and types	1. Introduction	1. Declaring variables 2. Variable type string 3. Variable type numer	Lists
Lists	1. Introduction	1. Declaring lists	Arithmetic operator
Arithmetic operator	1. Declaring variables	1. Addition 2. Subtraction 3. Multiplication 4. Modulo 5. Division 6. Power	String operators
String operators	1. Declaring variables	1. Adding strings 2. Multiplying strings	List operators
List operators	1. Declaring lists	1. Adding lists 2. Multiplying lists	String fromating
String formatting	1 Declaring variables 2. Variable type number 3. Variable type string	1. String formatting	Basic string operators
Basic string operators	1 Declaring variables 2. Variable type string	1. Char index 2. Count string occurrence 3. String slice 4. String split	Conditions
Conditions	1. Declaring variables	1. If statement 2. Boolean operators	Loops
Loops	1. Declaring variables 2. Decalring lists	1. For lopp 2. While loop	Loops 2
Loops 2	1. For loop 2. While loop	1. Break statement 2. Continue statement	Functions
Functions	1. Arithmetic operators 2. Loops 3. Conditions	1. Defining functions 2 Calling functions	Classes and bojects
Classes and objects	1. Defining functions 2. Calling functions	1. Defining classes 2. Creating objects	

Figure 1. Relation between lessons and concepts

In [1], it is given a clear definition of the set of lessons, concepts and student knowledge. Based on that, we propose here a new set of states, actions and rewards for implementing the pedagogical module as a reinforcement learning problem:

1. State(CurrL, Tc1, Tc2, Tc3, Tc4, Tc5, HasRc1, HasRc2, HasRc3, HasRc4, HasRc5) where:
 - a. CurrL has values from the set (0, L1, L2, ..., Ln) and shows what is the current lesson given to the student.
 - b. TC_i for $i \in [1,5]$ has values from (0, C1, C2, ... Cn) and shows what are the 5 concepts that are taught by the current lesson. TC_i may be 0 in cases when the lesson teaches less than 5 concepts. In the implementation, this is translated into a vector with length 5, with values 1 or 0, having the values [0,0,0,0,0] when the lesson teaches no concepts, and values [1,1,1,1,1] when the lesson teaches all 5 concepts.
 - c. $HasRc_i$ for $i \in [1,5]$ has value 0 or 1. $HasRc_i$ has the value 1 if the student knows TC_i and 0 otherwise. In the implementation, this is translated into a vector with length 5, with values 1 or 0, having the values [0,0,0,0,0] when the student has not learned any concept from the current lesson, and values [1,1,1,1,1] when the student has learned all 5 concepts of the current lesson.

Example of the state may be as follows:

[1,1,1,1,0,0,0,1,0,0,0,] where:

- a. Element in index 0, with value 1 shows the current lesson is Lesson 1.
 - b. Elements from index 1 to 5, show that the lesson 1 teaches only 3 concepts.
 - c. Element from 6 to 10, show that the student has learned only the first concept that is taught by this lesson.
2. Action (stay in current lesson, go to next lesson L_i) where:
 - a. Stay means that the student will be given again the current lesson.
 - b. L_i has values from (L_1, L_2, \dots, L_n). The system chooses the next lesson to give to the student based on current lesson and what is the next lesson that comes after it
 3. Rewards will be:
 - a. Negative value (-10) if the student has learned all the concepts that are taught by current lesson and the system gives again this lesson.
 - b. Positive value (+10) if the student has learned all the concepts that are taught by current lesson and the system gives the next lesson.
 - c. Negative value (-10) if the student has not learned all the concepts that are taught by current lesson and the system gives the next lesson.
 - d. Positive value (+10) if the student has not learned all the concepts that are taught by current lesson and the system gives again this lesson.

3. SIMULATION

Training an agent using reinforcement learning requires a very large number of episodes and trials that are not very suitable to perform with real life students. Because of this, we have done the training in a simulated environment, by simulating the behavior of real students. The system is composed of two parts: the tutor and the student. The tutor is the agent that will be trained using the reinforcement learning algorithm and will learn what is the best action to take in respect to the student’s current state. The student is a simulation of a real-life student. It has its knowledge base, that consists of concepts that it has learned or not and a parameter-learning probability-that describes its ability to learn new concepts. The learning probability gives the probability for learning a new concept. When the student is given a lesson, for every concept that this lesson teaches, the student learns this concept with probability equal to “learning probability” and does not learn this concept with probability equal to “1 - learning probability”. If the learning probability is 1, this means that the student always learns the concepts and if it is 0 the student never learns anything. In our simulation, when the student is given a lesson by the tutor, based on the learning probability, we simulate the fact that the student did or did not learn that concept.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We have used the DQN algorithm as given by [4], using memory replay and target network. Figure 2 gives the architecture of the target and train networks.

Layer(type)	OutputShape	Param#
dense_8(Dense)	(None,24)	288
dense_9(Dense)	(None,48)	1200
dense_10(Dense)	(None,24)	1176
dense_11(Dense)	(None,2)	50
Total params: 2,714		
Trainable params: 2,714		
Non-trainable params: 0		

Figure 2. The architecture of the neural network

We have done the training using two scenarios: 1. the student starts with no knowledge of any of the concepts for every episode, 2. the student starts with knowing random concepts for each episode. Regardless of which scenario is used, there are some hyper parameters that we keep the same and these are shown in Table 1.

TABLE I
HYPER PARAMETERS

Train frequency (after how many episodes will happen the training)	20
Maximal number of steps in episode	100
Learning probability of the simulated student	0.7
Learning rate	0.005
Batch size	64
Gamma	0.85
Maximal memory size	5000

One important aspect of the training process is the exploration of actions and states regardless of what the agent has learned until now. We have done the training by varying the level of exploration using:

1. Epsilon value that shows the probability with which the agent chooses a random action.
2. Epsilon decay is a value used to decrease the value of epsilon.
3. Minimum epsilon is the minimum value that epsilon can have.
4. Epsilon decay frequency determines after how many steps the value of epsilon will decrease.

The training is done for the two scenarios, by varying the parameters that determine the exploration level. We start with some parameters, perform the training for a certain number of episodes, then change the parameters and restart the training again using the network weights from the previous round. For every training done, as a result we give the total reward earned for each episode. Following we give the trainings that are done for each of the scenarios, the parameters used, and the reward earned.

4.1 Student starts with knowing no concepts for every episode.

We have performed two sets of training for this scenario, by varying the number of episodes for each round.

- a. The hyper parameters are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2
HYPER PARAMETERS FOR THE FIRST TRAINING OF THE FIRST SCENARIO

	1st Round	2nd Round	3rd Round	4th Round	5th Round	6th Round
Number of episodes	1000	2000	2000	1000	1000	1000
Initial epsilon	0.9	0.9	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.1
Epsilon decay	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995
Minimum epsilon	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Epsilon decay frequency	100	100	50	50	50	50
Results	Figure 3	Figure 4	Figure 5	Figure 6	Figure 7	Figure 8

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

b. The hyper parameters are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

HYPER PARAMETERS FOR THE SECOND TRAINING OF THE FIRST SCENARIO

	1st Round	2nd Round	3rd Round
Number of episodes	4000	4000	2000
Initial epsilon	0.9	0.5	0.2
Epsilon decay	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995
Minimum epsilon	0.01	0.01	0.01
Epsilon decay frequency	100	100	100
Results	Figure 9	Figure 10	Figure 11

Figure 9.

Figure 10.

Figure 11.

4.2 Student starts with knowing random concepts for every episode. For this scenario, the hyper parameters are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4

HYPER PARAMETERS FOR THE SECOND SCENARIO

	1st Round	2nd Round	3rd Round
Number of episodes	4000	4000	2000
Initial epsilon	0.9	0.6	0.2
Epsilon decay	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995
Minimum epsilon	0.01	0.01	0.01
Epsilon decay frequency	100	100	100
Results	Figure 12	Figure 13	Figure 14

Figure 12.

Figure 13.

Figure 14.

4.3 Testing

After we performed the training for both scenarios, we have tested the performance of each of the models learned by using them in simulations, for 100 episodes with a student with random concepts and learning probability the same as the one used during the training process. For each of the tests, we show the total reward received and the length of each episode. The results are given in the Figures 15 to 20.

Figure 15. Reward for every episode, for 1st set of the 1st scenario

Figure 16. Length for every episode, for 1st set of the 1st scenario

Figure 17. Reward for every episode, for 2nd set of the 1st scenario

Figure 18. Length for every episode, for 2nd set of the 1st scenario

Figure 19. Reward for every episode, for the 2nd scenario

Figure 20. Length for every episode, for the 2nd scenario

5. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have presented a model for an intelligent tutoring system and trained it using reinforcement learning with DQN algorithm. We performed the training in a simulated environment, by simulating the behavior of the student. Also, the training was performed using different hyper parameters for the model and using different scenarios for the student knowledge. As the training and the testing results show, we believe that it is better to perform the training with a student that starts with knowing random concepts for every episode. In this way, there is higher probability to reach more states, compared to the scenario where the student always starts with knowing no concepts. Also, as results show, when using random concepts, the agent starts to get a positive reward earlier in time, meaning that it is learning to take better decisions. Another important factor to keep into consideration is exploration. As we see from the results, it is important to start with high levels of exploration in the beginning of the training and reduce the exploration gradually as the agent starts to learn.

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Clustering Massive Packets using a Lock-Free Algorithm of Tree-Based Reduction on GPGPU

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Abstract— Recently, the inspection of huge traffic log is imposing a great burden on security analysts. Unfortunately, there have been few research efforts focusing on scalability in analysing very large PCAP file with reasonable computing resources. In this paper, we present Asura which is a huge PCAP analyzer using A Lock-Free Algorithm of Tree-Based Reduction on GPGPU. Asura's parallel packet dump inspection is based on task-based decomposition and therefore can handle massive threads for large PCAP file without considering tidy parameter selection in adopting data decomposition. Asura is designed to scale out in processing large PCAP file by taking as many threads as possible. Asura takes two steps. First, Asura extracts feature vector represented by associative containers of $\langle \text{sourceIP}, \text{destIP} \rangle$ pair. By doing this, the feature vector can be drastically small compared with the size of original PCAP files. In other words, Asura can reduce packet dump data into the size of unique $\langle \text{sourceIP}, \text{destIP} \rangle$ pairs (for example, in experiment, Asura's output which is reduced in first step is about 2a parallel clustering algorithm is applied for the feature vector which is represented as $\langle \text{sourceIP}, \text{destIP} \rangle, V[i]$ where $V[i]$ is aggregated flow vector. In second step, Asura adopts an enhanced Kmeans algorithm. Concretely, two functions of Kmeans which are (1)calculating distance and (2)relabeling points are improved for parallel processing.

Also, Asura uses a Lock-free technique of tree-based reduction for large scale clustering on GPGPU. Proposal method is divided into two steps: fine reduction and coarse reduction. In the first reduction step, the clustering program obtain $K * N$ intermediate array where K is the number of clusters and N is the number of blocks. In the following step, new mean value is calculated over N blocks. By doing this, the clustering program can evade using atomic instruction which causes lock contention in coping with large scale clusters. In experiment, the performance of native GPU kernel with atomic instruction, Thrust template libraries and proposal method is compared and evaluated. For your paper to be published in the conference proceedings, you must use this document as both an instruction set and as a template into which you can type your own text. If your paper does not conform to the required format, you will be asked to fix it.

(Abstract)

Keywords-component; Clustreing; Massive Packets; Lock-free Algorithm, Tree-based Reduction, GPGPU

I. INTRODUCTION

The scale of network traffic are growing year by year. Besides, as the emergence of sophisticated cyber attack such as APT (Advanced Persistent Threat), we are forced to cope with the detailed packet inspection as well as checking other traffic logs. Currently, the inspection of huge traffic log is imposing a great burden on security analysts. Traffic irregularities or traffic anomalies is usually described as the result of one or more occurrences which changes the normal flow of data. Anomaly detection is the process of finding patterns in the audit network traffic log which do not conform to legitimate or normal behavior. The design of an anomaly detection method relies on a baseline model which represents the normal behavior of network traffic. The model is generally trained using audit data extracted from traffic for which all items are labeled in advance as either normal or anomalous. However, labelling traffic data is often expensive and time-consuming partly because it requires human experts.

II. OVERVIEW

A. Task-based decomposition

If we want to transform code into a concurrent version, there are two ways. First one is data decomposition, in which the program cope with a large collection of data and can compute every chunk of the data independently. Second one is task decomposition, in which the process is partitioned into a set of independent tasks that threads can execute in any order. Data decomposition has some drawbacks. For example, the size of PCAP file varies according to the situation in which the file is dumped. Besides each divided process is NOT homogeneous. Asura adopts task-based parallel processing which is shown in Figure1. Asura's parallel packet dump inspection is based on task-based decomposition and therefore can handle massive threads for large PCAP file without considering tidy parameter selection in adopting data decomposition. Asura is designed to scale out in processing large PCAP file by taking as many threads as possible. Assume that we have n threads and each thread and each thread is

associated with one PCAP file. By doing this, Asura can take advantages of dynamic scheduling for coping with a variety of kinds and size of PCAP file. Asura consists of two thread sets: a master thread which enqueues the name of PCAP file and a worker thread which processes the each PCAP file. The master thread enqueues the list of PCAP file, and passes it to the worker thread. More specifically, the master thread traverses PCAP file directory and enqueue the file name. When the queue is full, the master thread waits until the worker thread processing packets consumes a file name and removes it from the queue. The worker (packet processing thread) dequeues a file name and parses the PCAP file. The task of the worker thread is flow vector aggregation using associative container discussed later in III-A.

Fig. 1. Task Decomposition

B. Features selection and structures

In general, most system of the identification of anomalies on traffic volume is based on features. The features could be many: source and destination addresses, port numbers, static signatures, statistics signatures and so on. The difficulty of the anomaly traffic identification is to handle the huge traffic volume. The challenging part here is to select which header item are worth and suitable to be learned. For simplicity, we pick up the five items as follows:

- Source and destination IP addresses: unique identifiers of sender and receiver.
- The number of captured packets: the fields is reflected by the traffic volume.
- TLEN (total length of packets): the 16-bit field definesvthe entire packet volume in bytes, including both header and data.
- TTL (The time-to-live): the time-to-live value can be referred as an upper bound on the time which an IP datagram can be processed.
- source and destination port: port number is checked for the type of application.

Structure is shown as follows. For each fields, the numerical fields of packet header are reduced using

associative container of map < key, value >. The key stores number of packets. In other words,

```

1: /* STRUCTURE II: reduced */
2: typedef struct _reduced {
3:   map<int, int> count;
4:   map<int, int> tlen;
5:   map<int, int> ttl;
6:   map<int, int> sport;
7:   map<int, int> dport;
8:   pthread_mutex_t mutex;
9: } reduced_t;
10: reduced_t reduced;
    
```

Another challenging part is to transform code into a concurrent version with massive multithreading. For reduction, we use the structure as follows.

```

1: /* STRUCTURE I: srcIP, destIP */
2: typedef struct _addrpair {
3:   map<string, string> m;
4:   pthread_mutex_t mutex;
5: } addrpair_t;
6: addrpair_t addrpair;
    
```


Fig. 2. Flow vector computation by multithreading

Here pthread mutex t is the notation for mutual execution. Mutual exclusion locks (mutexes) prevent multiple threads from simultaneously executing critical sections of code which access shared data (that is, mutexes are used to serialize the execution of threads). All mutexes must be global. Threads within the same process or within other processes can share mutexes. Mutexes can synchronize threads within the same process or in other processes. Mutexes can be used to synchronize threads between processes if the mutexes are allocated in writable memory and shared among the cooperating processes and have been initialized for this task.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Extracting feature vector using associative container

Associative containers are a generic group of class templates in the standard library of the C++ programming language which cope with ordered associative arrays. The containers are

implemented in the current revision of the C++ standard: set, map, multiset, multimap.

- Key uniqueness: in map and set each key must be unique.
- Element composition: in map and multimap each element should be composed from a key and a mapped value.
- Element ordering: elements must follow a strict weak ordering

B. K-Means

The k-Means algorithm iteratively partitions a given dataset into k clusters. It first selects k data points as the initial centroids, which could be the first k data points in the data set, or a set of randomly chosen k data points. For the k-Means problem, an integer k and a set of n data points $x \in R^d$ are given. Then, next step is to choose k centers C so as to minimize the potential function, Choosing these centers implicitly defines a clustering for each center. Proposed method set one cluster to be the set of data points that are closer to that center than to any other. As noted above, finding an exact solution to the K-Means problem is NP-hard. The K-Means method is a simple and fast algorithm that attempts to locally improve an arbitrary k-means clustering. It works as follows:

- 1) (initialization) Arbitrary choose k initial centers $C = c_1, \dots, c_k$.
- 2) (Distance Calculation) For each $i \in 1, \dots, k$, set the cluster C_i to be the set of points in X that are closer to C_i than they are to c_j for all $j \neq i$.
- 3) (Centroid Recalculation) For each $i \in 1, \dots, k$, set C_i to be the center of mass of all points in C_i
- 4) (Coverage Condition) Repeat steps 2 and 3 until no longer changes.

It is standard practice to choose the initial centers uniformly at random from x. Steps 2 and 3 are both guaranteed to decrease ϕ , so the algorithm makes local improvements to an arbitrary clustering until it is no longer possible to do so.

IV. TWO-STAGE REDUCTION FOR K-MEANS

Proposed method is divided into two procedures: fine reduction and coarse reduction. Fine reduction takes means as input while coarse reduction takes sums as parameter.

A. Parallel Reduction Pattern

Reduction is described as of the popular patterns for codifying best practices for software engineering. Reduction is an operation for combining every element in a collection into a unique element by invoking an associative combiner function. The reduce pattern enables us to summarize data by combing all the elements in a collection into a unique element usually by parallel reduction. Parallel reduction is performed by

associative and commutative operation. A combiner operator is used to combine all the elements of a collection pairwise.

The reduce pattern allows data to be summarized; it combines all the elements in a collection into a single element using some associative combiner operator. Figure 3 has four iterations with stride decreasing by $2 * N$. Terminate condition here is index = 0. At the first iteration, threads 0, 1, 2, 3 are launched. At the second iteration, two threads (0, 1) are launched. Finally, single thread (0) is invoked. Then, the unique value reduced from input array is obtained.

Fig. 3. Basic tree-based reduction. The calculation of the sum is iterated four times in parallel.

Fig. 4. Data representation of fine reduction. The input data size is $1024 * M$ where M is the number of blocks. The program obtains the $5 * M$ output arrays.

B. Fine Reduction Pattern

Fine reduction generates sums $sum[x,y]$ in $block[y]$ each cluster[x]. Therefore, shared memory size of fine reduction is the number of threads * 3. Fine reduction executes blockwise reduction, which means it outputs $b * k$ data points where b is the number of blocks and k is the number clusters. Figure 4 show the data representation of fine reduction. For each block, the data $[g_i]$ is reduced to $sum[i,b]$ where g_i is global index. Figure 4 also shows data representation of input and output of fine reduction. In input, each block has 1024 threads for coping with each data point. In output, inputs are reduced to $1 * K$ array for each block where K is the number of clusters.

Fine reduction is divided into two steps: new cluster assignment and calculating the new sum which is a case of generic K-Means algorithm. At first, it takes $data_x, data_y, \{mean_x \text{ and } mean_y\}$ of each cluster as input and calculates

the shortest distance. Once the shortest distance is figured out and the new cluster is assigned, this reduction module calculates `new_sum_x`, `new_sum_y` according to the new clusters.

Fire reduction is divided into two loops. Besides, first loop has one branch and second loop is two branches. First loop aims to calculate the shortest distance for the nearest cluster of each point and assign the new cluster to the point. Second loop aims to calculate the new sum of each cluster (K). First branch at line 28-31 is responsible for the reduction for each block. Second branch at line 33-37 is responsible for terminate condition. If the `local_index` is 0, this means final reduced value is stored to `new_sums_x[cluster_index]`.

Fig. 5. Data representation of coarse reduction. After the fine reduction, the input data size is $N * M$ where N is the number of blocks and M is the number of clusters.

C. Coarse Reduction Pattern

Once the fine reduction is done, the next step is to obtain $K * N$ sequences where K is the number of cluster and N is the number of blocks as shown in Figure 5. Coarse reduction figures out the sum of data points for each cluster. Note that the program performs the assignment and block-wise reduction in the same kernel. Then, the program invokes a coarse reduction to sum the block-wise values into a final, single value: Recall that in the fine reduction step, each block produces one sum per cluster. As such, you can visualize the input to the coarse reduction like this: The goal is to combine all these values into k sums, by summing up the individual, block-wise cluster sums (i.e. have one sum for each k_i). To do so, the program simply stop the reduction at stride k , as you can see in the code above. Figure 3 shows the data representation of coarse reduction. At the beginning of coarse reduction, the program have $K * N$ array where K is the number of cluster and N is the the number of blocks.

V. EXPERIMENT

A. Case1: Atomic Instructions

By using the `atomicAdd` function, programmer can rewrite the `incr` kernel. This instruction atomically add a value $V[i]$ to the value stored at memory location M . The updated `incr` kernel adopts a statement to increment the value stored at the

location pointer P . Then the instruction below return the values saved at pointer P before the increment operation.

```
__global__ void incr(__global__ int *ptr) { int temp = atomicAdd( ptr, 1); }
```

B. Case2: CUDA Thrust Template Library

CUDA Thrust is a C++ template library based on the Standard Template Library (STL). Thrust makes is possible to implement high performance parallel applications with reasonable effort by a high-level application interface. Thrust has a rich collection of data parallel primitives such as scan, sort, and reduce. Thrust provides two vector containers, `host_vector` and `device_vector`. The `host_vector` is stored in host memory while `device_vector` lives in GPU device memory. Many of algorithms provided by Thrust direct analogs in the STL.

C. Case3: Fine-Coarse Reduction

Reductions in serial execution like the averaging performed during the update step scale linearly. However, parallel reductions can be implemented efficiently by using two-stage tree-reduction: fine and coarse reduction. Key point in fine-coarse reduction is averaging is not performed over all our data. Instead, for each cluster, the points assigned to each cluster should be averaged. There are a few tricks for solving this problem. For doing this, the program can sort the data by their assignment, so that points in the same cluster are next to each other in memory. Then program can do one standard reduction per segment by decreasing the stride.

Fig. 6. Computing time with respect to the number of iterations. At the number of iterations 175, proposed method (fine-coarse) is about 2-4 times faster.

D. Reduction

Figure 6 show a comparison of algorithms of case 1, case 2 and case 3 in performing K-Means. In experiment, the scalability of proposed three algorithms is investigated in the case where the number of iterations is increasing. As data size constant with scaling the number of iterations remains the same, it is observed that proposed method of fine-coarse reduction outperforms two other algorithms.

Figure 7 displays comparison of computing time concerning the number of data points. The comparison of case 1, case2 and case 3 in running K-means is depicted. It turns to be clear that case 1 (atomic) and case 3 (fine-coarse) keeps the constant while the case 2 (thrust) is increasing linearly.

Fig. 7. Computing time with respect to the number of data points. During the iteration 1-175, proposed method remains constant computing time.

VI. RELATED WORK

Clustering which is grouping of similar objects [1] is one of the most popular procedures in data mining [2]. There are many practical applications of clustering such as unsupervised classification and taxonomy generation [3], nearest neighbor searching [4], scientific discovery [5], vector quantization [6], time series analysis [7], and multidimensional visualization [8,9,10]. However, there have been few research efforts in the view point of a large scale graph mining. There are many research efforts on parallelizing data mining algorithms such as association rules and classification. To name a few, Agrawal and Shafer [11], Chattratichat et al. [12], Cheung and Xiao [13], Han, Karypis, and Kumar [14]. Based on these works., the thrust of our paper is that how to parallelize edge contraction is focused. There are two main approaches for making Kmeans able to cluster very large datasets. The first approach is based on sampling and coresets extraction. A coreset is a small set of instances that is representative of the properties of the original data[15]. The second approach is to modify Kmeans to reduce resource utilization and scalability[16]. The third approach is applying preprocess such as PCA and dimension reduction before clustering process[17]. Compared with these research efforts, the novelty of our paper is the proposal of an effective pre-processing of a large scale graph clustering using parallel edge contraction.

Clemens et al. propose an approach for centroid update by combining point assignment and centroid updating [18]. A study of synchronization strategies mainly concerning concurrent data structures is shown in [19]. Zechner et al. propose parallelizing the distance calculation on GPU [20]. Lock-based synchronization scheme which allows lock stealing

within individual warps is proposed in [21]. Xu et al. propose software transactional memory leveraged by a hierarchical validation and encounter-time lock-sorting mechanism [22].

Concurrency and synchronization is important research topic in parallelism. In [23], a large empirical study of the concurrent behavior of deployed GPUs is conducted. [24] propose a technique for measurement and analysis of lock contention which processes data associated with locks about the idleness of spinning threads. Pan et al. present a method for allowing predicting the contention under the queue delegation locking algorithm [25]. In [26], Daniel et al. present a systematic research of synchronization strategies, mainly focusing on concurrent data structures.

VII. CONCLUSION

Recently, the inspection of huge traffic log is imposing a great burden on security analysts. Unfortunately, there have been few research efforts focusing on scalability in analyzing very large PCAP file with reasonable computing resources. Asura is full-scratch (and painful) implementation with POSIX Pthreads and C++ STL. PCAP files are NOT organized in a regular pattern or the parsing of PCAP files is different or unpredictable for each element in the stream. Leveraging Pthreads which represents assembly language in parallelism provides maximum flexibility. Asura adopts taskbased implementation for processing huge, heterogeneous and unpredictable PCAP file stream.

Asura the lock-free algorithm of tree-based reduction for evading the lock contention which causes the serious speed down in concurrent programming. Proposal method is divided into two steps: fine reduction and coarse reduction. In the first reduction step, the program obtain $K * N$ intermediate array where K is the number of clusters and N is the number of blocks. In the following step, new mean value is calculated over N blocks. Proposal method enables us to avoid using atomic instruction which causes lock contention in coping with large scale clusters. In experiment, the performance of native GPU kernel with atomic instruction, Thrust template libraries and proposal method is compared and evaluated. Proposal method is adopted for K-Means which processes the large number of data points. It has become clear that proposal method outperforms the conventional method with the atomic instruction in scaling both the number of data points and iterations. There are many discussions about the drawback of lock contention in both multi-core CPU and GPGPU.

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Node Mobility Optimization in Multi-hop WBAN Using Genetic Algorithm

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Abstract— Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN) is an uprising innovation for short-range remote communication inside, on or circular the body, within the fundamental for therapeutic applications. In this paper, an adjuvant scheme has been proposed to increase the node mobility in WBAN. Dead nodes, path loss, low residual energy, and less throughput are the main causes for decreasing mobility of nodes. A comparative study has been done between the existing and proposed multi-hop protocol using the Genetic Algorithm and Fuzzy logic. This proposed model has been simulated in MATLAB simulator.

Keywords—WBAN, Node Mobility, Genetic Algorithm, Fuzzy logic.6

I. INTRODUCTION

WBAN as a facilitator and information collector, for the reason of real-time checking of patients' physiological parameters, such as ECG, EEG, blood weight and so forward. With the aging of the individuals, remaining therapeutic assets cannot delight future healthcare stresses of seniors and patients. Assets are lacking and it is incomprehensible for most noteworthy patients to oversee to pay for long-term clinic breaks due to money-related confinements, work, and other points of interest, indeed even though their health ion must be checked in a real-time [1] or brief discontinuous time mode. the result, remote observing restorative plans will get to be a portion of versatile healthcare middles with real-time nursing within the future. In WBANs, sensor nodes are worked with constrained vitality sources. It is required to utilize the least control for transmitting information from sensor nodes to the sink. One of the major impediments in WBAN is to energize the batteries. An efficient directing convention is required to overcome this issue of energizing batteries. Depending on QoS parameters a therapeutic master will give the command to enact appropriate activity in case circumstance isn't ordinary. In WBAN, different remote communication innovations like Zigbee, Bluetooth, 2.4 GHz ISM band, and Intra-body communication are conveyed to exchange the information between all the sensors and facilitator hub [2]. But in WBAN not at all like WSN, there is the number of impediments like battery control, scope run, receiving wire stature of the handset, heterogeneous exchange rates, tall flag weakening, etc. [2] But transmission with tall QoS parameters like least impedances, tall bundle conveyance proportion (PDR), tall throughput, least, expended vitality, low idleness, tall connect unwavering quality, etc. is the extreme prerequisite due to their application fields. A few creators have distinguished the alternative network which known as follows:

(a) Simply get to and consolation [3]: WBAN nodes are put on the patient body surface or are covered beneath their cloth. Little estimates and low taken a toll are required.

(b) Real-time preparing [1]: Body Area Network is utilized, enlisting patient physiological exercises, activities, which may happen proper schedule [3, 4]. Its necessity directed to its applications which exchanged made strides unwavering quality and vitality utilization.

(c) Portability demands [3]: In this network, clients have free mobility. Hence, the nodes shared by the same portability design regarded the outside door. These body sensors given successfully handled by the central sink.

In this paper, our target is to optimize the node mobility of WBAN. WBAN nodes use a limited energy source to keep nodes alive for a long time. Node mobility always increases the performance of WBANs whereas long-distance route decreases throughput. By using the multi-hop node protocol moving distance between nodes can reduce the path. In this paper our goals are:

- ❖ To minimize the dead nodes
- ❖ To increase the residual energy
- ❖ To reduce the path loss
- ❖ To increase the throughput
- ❖ To determine the suitable path for next node selection

II. WBAN CHARACTERISTICS

WBAN is used mainly in the medical sector to observe the patient's condition. WBAN network is used in the human or animal body by placing tiny Bio-Medical-sensor nodes [5]. Network sensor nodes send all the data to the sink to transmit to authority or doctor. This network is used to provide the best services to patients from a long distance. Nowadays WBAN system is used by general peoples for monitoring their health condition by wearable devices like a smartwatch, smart shoes, digital glasses, etc. Day by day exercises like running and walking and physiological exercises just like the pulse and respiratory have an impact on the remote engendering significantly [6][7].

2.1.1 A typical WBAN scheme contains

- ❖ A small networks around the body

- ❖ A sink connecting to a different kind of network which will be another node with routing and data mixture options
- ❖ An organization like website or computing setup
- ❖ Software for health care authority to give better services

Figure-1: A typical WBAN architecture.

III. RELATED WORKS

In the paper Blumrosen Et Al. [8] Body sensors need to be small, lightweight, noninvasive, and wireless-enabled and must consume low power when operational. The batteries can be effectively changeable by the patient own or medical Authority, the sensor will be still operational when the batteries have low energy. A WSN will be a comfortable wear for a patient and anyone can change without professional skill and no need to implement proper position. When conductive equipment is made with organic e-textiles and wireless-enabled technology.

Saleem Et AL. [9] and Kumar and Lee [10] identified some attacks that can be dangerous to the remote medical system at MAC, the physical and transport layer. Different types of medical equipment have different types of data rate capabilities, so the network needs enough bandwidth to support the whole operation and needs the best network protocols. Sensing, processing, transceiver, and power these four small components are used to make up a sensor node. The transceiver used the most power in the sensor node. To reduce the power consumption all the nodes must be used as autonomous operation. Multi-path can reduce power consumption. From the other viewpoint, WBANs must be highly secured to protect personal data and medical data. To collect sensitive data and utilize them in a secure system used a high algorithm to protect from dangerous Trojan attacks, to protect from hackers.

From all previous discussions, WBANs need tiny wireless WSN nodes around or in the body, quick real-time processing [3,4]. The nodes are will be flexible and easy to use by patients. The consumption will not be critical if the batteries are easy to changeable. Dependability, mobility, and data encryption must be support by WBANs.

IV. PROPOSED METHOD

WBANs can impressively spare costs and time for each healthcare experts and patients since of the quality of patients and situation independent recognition. A parcel of as of late, the capacity administration downside has been tended to victimization hypothesis of recreations, for the occasion, in CDMA systems and conveyed systems Remote dispersed miniaturized scale sensor frameworks can modify blame

tolerant recognition and administration of a run of applications.

In the present Holter Monitory system shown in figure 2, which combines with lots of wire and it is not even user friendly. Also, the Battery backup only 24hours which is another drawback of the device.

Figure-2: Present monitoring system

Additionally, a few WBAN structures have been effectively tried, particularly in health monitoring uses. In these structures, the Wireless sensor nodes put over body surface could be a smart phone or a personal digital assistant (PDA) which can work as a transceiver and operated by human. In these types of situation, the PDA acts as a sink hub; this is a portion of the WBAN can connect to the healthcare center by Any cellular networks such as GSM, CDMA,EDGE, WCDMA, Portable WiMAX, or other wireless technologies.

Figure-3: Mobility-free WBAN architecture approach.

To increase the mobility of WBAN these types of connectivity are very crucial. Figure 3 presents the modern methodology of mobility-free WBAN engineering. At WBAN part sensor nodes are implanted over human body and connect the application part with any mobile technology. It can support stationary or mobile modes both. It can be implemented with other application without any resources on WBAN. In this research [11], the authors prove the potential of using RSSI capacities on the kinematic human body. Figure 4 shows the Flowchart of the proposed model. In this flowchart first WBAN Testbed area needs to be selected. Then the nodes will be initialized with their coverages. After that source and destination path will be determined and

Genetic Algorithm (GA) will be initiated to ensure the optimal route. After that, Function's fitness will be checked according to Fuzzy Logic.

Figure-4: Flowchart of the proposed model.

This Proposed method would be user-friendly and it will reduce in-hospital stays that can reduce waste of time. Another important point can be noted here that continuous monitoring may help in early detection which may prevent from falling into critical situation in a short span of time.

WBANs are application-dependent, being by and large categorized into two kinds: (i) event discovery and (ii) periodic result. Within the to begin with, the nodes send information as it were when an event happens whereas within the moment the nodes send information at intermittent intervals. An individual instance of the organized topology, both the nodes' resources and the information sent are diverse. One of the foremost critical things in planning measures for WBANs is adjusting of QoS imperatives with low power control limitations of nodes. A few standards have been adopted for medical sector applications like Bluetooth (IEEE 802.15.1) or ZigBee (IEEE 802.15.4) protocols. These remote standards are well archived and tried but are not well-organized cause the target systems that are more adaptable and are utilized for longer transmission areas. This makes them less energy productive than protocols that are particularly architecture for a WBAN (e.g., 802.15.6) [12].

V. SIMULATION AND ANALYSIS

This investigation has been conducted by using GA (Genetic algorithm) for the optimization of node mobility in WBAN.

Here Sensor Node Classification (SNC) scheme has been performed. Genetic algorithm, also known as a global heuristic algorithm, which estimates an optimal solution through generating different individuals. It mainly performs three steps for checking i.e., Mutation, Crossover, and Genesis. The first step mutation is used for conserving and introducing diversity in GA. It is a genetic operator, which maintains genetic diversity from one generation of a population of genetic algorithm chromosomes to the next. In the next step crossover is applied which mainly used for the matching [13]. In our proposed model algorithm, this is the most important part. Only the trusted nodes will be passes through the next step for fitness check. Genesis is the concluding component of GA which is used for mutation and crossover formula in the programming section [13]. This methodology can be operated in training which trains the input pattern and testing which is used to test the individual nodes in WBAN network. The classification is done by using Fuzzy logic. The work is being tried on parameters such as network lifetime, throughput, BER (Bit error rate), path loss, and residual energy, etc.

The following are the steps that illustrate the proposed model that has to be finished.

Step 1: Design WBAN by space of height and dimension of 100×100.

Step 2: Initialize the detector nodes within the WBAN. Within the planned work, we tend to implement fifty varieties of detector nodes.

Step 3: The WBAN coverage space is initialized by utilizing the supply node and destination node within the WBAN.

Step 4: With the routing protocol, the route is being discovered by the info transmission of the supply node towards the destination node.

Step 5: For optimizing the route, the simplest route optimization algorithmic program named as a genetic algorithmic program is applied.

Step 6: If the GA fitness performs is true as per the symbolic logic rule set then a unique route is developed between supply and destination otherwise the node is rejected and checks another node within the WBAN.

Step 7: A supreme test is made among supply and goal, the execution measurements like vitality utilization, bit blunder rate, throughput, and delay inside the arrangement have been measured.

Throughput: It is named as the total number of packet send within the recreation time. It can be clarified numerically as [14]:

$$\text{Throughput} = \frac{\sum \text{Packets sent}}{\text{Total data packets}}$$

BER (Bit Error rate): BER is characterized as the number of bits transmitted per unit time [15].

$$BER = \frac{\text{Bit errors}}{\text{total number of transferred bit during an interval}}$$

Energy Utilization: Vitality utilization is named as the full vitality being exchanged by each hub in WBAN at changed arrange layers. It is characterized scientifically as underneath:
 $n-1$

$$\text{Energy Consumption} = \sum_{i=0} (\text{Energy_consumed_by_node})$$

End to end delay within the numerical term is characterized as the overall time being slipped by for the bundle information transmission.

$$D_{\text{end-end}} = D_{\text{trans}} + D_{\text{prop}} + D_{\text{proc}}$$

Where $D_{\text{end-end}}$ = End-To-End Delay

D_{trans} = Transmission Delay

D_{prop} = Propagation

Delay D_{proc} = Processing Delay

VI. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In our paper mesh topology has been considered to deploy the sensor network. Mesh topology provides robustness, short path selection, high data transferring rate.

Figure-5: Deployment of sensor nodes.

Figure-5 shows the deployment of sensor nodes in WBAN. This deployment is simulated in MATLAB and considering the number of nodes is 8 where 6 are active nodes and 2 dead nodes. The green circles are considered as active node and the red circles denote the dead nodes. We analyzed the WBAN network using MULTI-HOP and showed the performance graphs of path loss, residual energy, packets received at the sink by using 8 nodes in Figures 5, 6, 7, and 8.

Figure-6: Analysis of network lifetime.

Figure-7: Analysis of throughput

Figure-8: Analysis of residual energy

Figure-9: Path loss

Proposed Fuzzy Logic for Node Mobility:

We considered 3 main network nodes and 3 sub-nodes each of them. We put different values for different ranges for those all nodes. In Fuzzy logic, we have set rules in the Mamdani rule box. By setting individual rules for each node we have distributed a specific range for the system. The output shows the surfaces between two nodes concerning those rules.

Figure-10: Adding 3 Main nodes, Mamdani rule scope, and output scope.

Figure 10 shows three example nodes and output scope for Mobility analysis. Three nodes have different ranges. After adding rules in the Mamdani rule box. A node can define the best path for forwarding nodes which can increase mobility.

Figure-11: Created simulation rules in Fuzzy logic

Figure-12: Created simulation rules in Fuzzy logic.

Figure 12 shows the rules which are created in the Mamdani rule box. Here the ranges are, node-1=2.5, node-2=7.5 and node-3=12.5. Figures 11,12 and 13 show the surface graphs of 3 nodes.

Figure-13: Surface graph of node 2, 1.

Figure-14: Surface graph of node 3, 2

Figure-15: Surface graph of Node-3, 1

Our observation from this work is to increase the time of alive nodes in Multi-hop. It also increases throughput to transmit

higher data to the sink. This topology decreases the energy drain and pathloss for a short link. On the other hand, in the Mamdani-Fuzzy logic technique, we can create our own oriented rules for the distribution of nodes and determine the best path for transmission in WBAN. By using this technique WBAN gets low power consumption, minimized dead node, and overlapping. Without the Fuzzy logic technique, we can't easily get the data transfer path or next node selection for WBAN.

Figure-16: Comparison of nodes lifetime between Existing and Proposed WBAN.

From node mobility analysis we observed some improvement in WBAN. Figure 16 shows the comparison of nodes lifetime between existing and proposed WBAN. Here multihop protocol reduces the node forwarding path. We can conclude that here increased the nodes' lifetime by 13.13%.

Figure-17: Comparison of residual energy between Existing and Proposed WBAN.

Figure 17 shows the comparison of residual energy between existing and proposed WBAN. For reducing the node forwarding path the energy abstains from consumption. Here we can conclude that the residual energy increased by 8.87% than before.

Figure-18: Comparison of path loss between Existing and Proposed WBAN.

In figure-18 the comparison of path loss between existing and proposed WBAN is shown. Here we observed that the path loss decreased in the proposed protocol. So we can conclude that the path loss decreased by 17.53%.

Figure-19: Comparison of throughput between Existing and Proposed WBAN.

Figure-19 shows the comparison of throughput between existing and proposed WBAN. Here increased throughput by 47.11%.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a Genetic Algorithm in the field of WBAN using a multi-hop protocol. WBAN framework is introduced in clinics and the framework could be three-level engineering which comprises of Medical Server, Individual Server, Sensor nodes and all levels have it possess usefulness to total the method of WBAN. Specialists utilizing their gadgets with the assistance of the web can check their patients and indeed the patients who are being introduced with sensors moreover require web networks in their gadgets like portable phones, PDAs, etc. Simulation results have shown the effectiveness of the proposed model. Using multi-hop rule in GA gave the best possible route among various possible routes in the shortest period. It also improved Throughput, Packet delivery ratio, Residual energy consumed by nodes, and increased network lifetime. In the future, within the WBAN frameworks which are introduced in clinics require security which is the major issue nowadays. Security issues like confirmation, patient's e-reports that are spared within the cloud database is to be moved forward by utilizing any best optimization method. Patients don't need to uncover their individual life's issues with any obscure individual. On the off chance that the persistent who is having any inveterate infection like Asthma, Alzheimer illness, Helps, Cancer or any other infection which he/she don't want to talk about with any other, so there's the zone where security is the major concern

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IP CAMERA A TOOL FOR EFFECTIVE SURVEILLANCE SYSTEM

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Abstract

IP surveillance is an important part of every modern security system which augments the protection of assets, homes and industrial facilities. Over the past decades, it has become part of internet of things (IoT). As the names implies, IP surveillance is a network solution where each camera is made up of its own IP address and password. This solution offers several advantages because it is built on a network; it is scalable and offers flexible installation and placement. It uses cost effective cat 6 cabling, which carries power, video, audio, PTZ (Plan, Tilt, Zoom) and event data. Remote viewing and management is integrated. This article explains the role of IP cameras in effective surveillance systems.

INTRODUCTION

Technology is part of our daily lives; we have become accustomed to it that we are confident in its security and privacy. A typical example is the surveillance system which has prevented many miscreants' intrusion into our system almost in all facets of our world.

Surveillance cameras are video cameras used for the purpose of observing an area. They are often connected to a recording device or IP network, and may be watched by a security guard or law enforcement officer. Cameras and recording equipment used to be relatively expensive and required human personnel to monitor camera footage, but analysis of footage has been made easier by automated software that

organizes digital video footage into a searchable database, and by video analysis software.

In response to the demands for quick, efficient and reliable services, industry players are increasingly deploying technology as a means of generating insights into customers' behavioural patterns and preferences. Well developed outsourcing support functions (technology and operations) are increasingly being used to provide services and manage costs

Presently, IP cameras with network interfaces have become widely available from an increasing number of manufacturers, with high definition image quality and sophisticated camera functionalities. These cameras are directly attached to a data network, such as a local or wide area network from where the camera is then directly accessed and viewed from a computer on the network.

Building block of an IP Camera

However, there is a serious setback with the use of IP cameras in surveillance of systems, despite its wide use; there is every tendency and fear that it will succumb to threats.

IP cameras

There are different types of surveillance cameras, these types are used for different purposes, and most common among them are the CCTV cameras and the IP cameras. Although IP cameras have enormous characteristics that supersede CCTV cameras, their reliability are not trusted. The table below compares IP cameras characteristics with that of analog systems during video surveillance system performance(Memos et'al, 2018).

Table 1: Compares IP cameras characteristics with that of analog systems

	Scenario with analog cameras	Scenario with IP cameras
Camera resolution	From 420 to 700 TV lines, 4CIF resolution	From 1 Mpixel to 8 MPixel
Cabling (Video and Power)	Coaxial to each camera and DVR, additional power cables	Cat 5e, Power over Ethernet (PoE)
The average cable length	100 m/camera (video) 65 m/camera (Power)	65 m/camera (Cat5 with(PoE))
Power	Power for Cameras	PoE
Switches	To all types DVR	PoE switch
Server / memory	Mid-end DVR (H.264 compatible with memory)	PC (standard) with memory
Software	On the DVR (H.264 compatible)	AxIS Camera Station
Monitor	Standard high resolution monitors	Standard high resolution monitors

CCTV cameras are preferred to IP cameras because of the belief that IP cameras may at times be threatened and used by fraudsters as a spy. With the advancement in technology, IP cameras have dominated because of their complex benefits, which transform the video signals inside the cameras into a digital form, in contrast to the older types of cameras (Alshalawi & Alghamdi, 2017)(Gradimirka et'al, 2013).

The IP camera is resident on the local area network (LAN). Video data is transmitted through the LAN to a video server that routes the videos to end users and mass storage server.

PROS AND CONS

IP cameras are the least secure CCTV system, but may have application where remote viewing over a network is desired or where a high bandwidth network exists. With an IP camera system, a network connection between the sites is all that is required to view any camera image on the system. However, they cost more than a standard analogue non IP camera.

Overview of IP surveillance system

An IP surveillance system can be simple or complicated, depending on the need. A simple scenario when one wants to view and record video will be connecting a personal computer to an Ethernet cable and then to network switch which allows different devices to be connected also and a cable from the switch is connected to the camera location. Then equipment that can capture video and send stream over network is needed, which is a network camera or an analog camera connected to a video encoder, this is sometimes known as a video server. Below is a diagram showing an overview of an IP surveillance system.

Overview of IP surveillance system

IP video Surveillance Systems

IP Surveillance refers to a security system that presents a user the ability to monitor and record video/audio over an Internet Protocol based computer network such as a local area network or the internet (IP Surveillance Design Guide, 2008). IP Surveillance sometimes also known as network video or IP CCTV uses the IP Network technology as the backbone for transporting information.

Conclusion

IP cameras are susceptible to attacks, although they have many characteristics. As a result of these characteristics and with the growth in technology, IP cameras are widely used.

As a result of the digital nature and method of video distribution, IP based surveillance systems introduce a host of advanced functionalities that enhance greater control and management of live and recorded video data

thereby making them highly suitable for security surveillance applications. Some of these include remote accessibility, high image quality, easy and future proof integration, scalability, flexibility, cost effectiveness, event management and intelligent video

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Case Based Reasoning Approach for Market Basket Analysis on the Performance of Issuers in the Home Appliances Industry Sector

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Abstract:—The recommendation system (decision support) is an important part of various types of software application development. The recommendation based on a case-based approach aims to overcome the limitations of user insights and to make it easier to provide an overview of item patterns. The study was conducted using five companies in the consumer goods sector in the household appliances sub-sector. The study tested Case Based Reasoning to predict financial conditions and know the association of products to find out the composition patterns in Market Basket Analysis. The research sample is five household appliances sub-sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The value of similiarity of results from case based to predict the company's financial performance in 2019 can be explained using five ratio indicators. The results of the distribution of financial performance descriptions can provide a recommendation system in the form of indentifying companies with hight profits, asset management, product differentiations and explaining the characteristics of companies with low profits.

Keywords: *Case Based Reasoning, Market Basket Analysis, Company Performance.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The home appliance industry is predicted to simultaneously increase in line with the development of the property, tourism and hospitality industry in Southeast Asia. In 2014 more than 9.5 million foreign tourists visited Indonesia. In an effort to accommodate the arrival of international tourists to Indonesia, more than 15,000 rooms valued at more than Rp 1.5 trillion were built [1].

As a case in point, a number of households began to buy two-tube washing machines for the first time, while some residents with middle to upper economic levels began to replace washing machines with greater capacity and better technology. National economic growth accompanied by an increase in

purchasing power is a major factor in the predictor of increased sales of household appliances[2].

The increasing challenges of companies in capitalizing the household appliances market, the company's performance becomes quite important. Parameters that can be used in appraising company performance appropriately are by analyzing information from financial statements.

One of technique to determine the association between products is used Market Basket Analysis (MBA). The MBA works by finding combinations of items that often appear together in transaction reports. The function of the MBA is to identify the relationship between consumers and goods purchased [3].

Case Based Reasoning (CBR) is a problem solving paradigm that is closely related to the way of thinking in situations when facing new problems. CBR uses old experience to solve new problems. This research presents an analytical approach and recommendations in cases where company performance is adjusted on the set of items for each product. CBR is the right method because the set of product items in each company is modeled equally.

The recommendation system (decision support) is an important part of various types of software application development. The case-based recommendation approach aims to overcome the limitations of the user's insight and to make it easier to provide an overview of the item's pattern. The recommendation technique tends to give a decision on the similarity of types and patterns of similarity of old cases based on the hypothesis that the value of the item is stable in a certain period of time.

Previous research from Gatzoura and Sanchez-Marre (2015) [4] can analyze consumer behavior revealed from the basketball market structure patterns. An MBA can refer to the search for associations so that it can give meaning to a company's financial performance. In this association, it can also be known patterns of relationships between entity indicators. The study was conducted using five companies engaged in the consumer goods sector household appliances sub-sector. The study examines Case Based Reasoning to find out the similiarity of financial conditions and to know

the association of products to find out the composition patterns in Market Basket Analysis.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This study refers to previous research from Alfonso, Javier, Fernand, Enrique, and Juan on "Energy Optimization Using a Case-Based Reasoning Strategy", in 2018. In this study describes how researchers review problems that occur in several houses and offices in utilizing energy for Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems researchers used the CBR (Case Based Reasoning) method to find solutions to problems associated with forming a multi- architectural system with a wireless sensor network and studying user habits and use of artificial neural networks. This system is considered to be able to save energy by 41% [5].

The next research is from Rahman, Slamet, Darmalaksana, Eclipse and Ramdhani on "Expert System for Deciding a Solution of Mechanical Failure in a Car using Case-based Reasoning" in 2019. In this study discuss the problem of the proper handling of car mechanics for complaints consumers for this research use an expert system with the CBR method to create four functions, namely taking the same problem, reusing knowledge, revising solutions and maintaining experience to strengthen the best solution. This system was built with Object-oriented Software Engineering (OOSE). With the system offered is expected to be able to provide solutions for the mechanics to work in accordance with the problems and also this system can be used for the development of other knowledge [6].

In the two previous studies, researchers studied how to approach the old problem to determine the solution of the problem at this writing, but in this paper is different from the two studies above because this research uses a decision support system as well as the calculation of similarity using the Tversky Method approach.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The stages of the research carried out are as follows;

a. Theoretical Basis

The author conducted a review sourced from reference books, journals and websites to obtain basic theories related to the subject matter to complete this research data.

1) Case Based Reasoning (CBR)

Case-based reasoning (CBR) is the process of solving new problems based on solutions from similar past problems. CBR reasoning is case-based by making analogous solutions. CBR is computer-based reasoning that can solve problems from data distribution in general. CBR development can be continued in the form of prototypes and explored cognitively. CBR is

identical to the rules of induction algorithm in machine learning. CBR begins by identifying a series of cases and training data. The case then forms an implicit generalization and establishes the similarity of characteristics between the case taken with the target problem [7].

Without statistically relevant data to support the generalization of research results there is no guarantee that the CBR process will proceed accordingly. CBR can be developed in a formal statistical framework to form inferences of various cases. Thus the CBR can produce similarity of new cases with high confidence [8]. The ultimate goal of CBR is to provide enough encoding so that it can be claimed in the form of similarity.

2) Market Basket Analysis (MBA)

Market Basket Analysis (MBA) is a modeling technique that is based on the concept that if a user uses certain items then there is a limited association then that user is likely to decide to look for these limitations elsewhere. The set of items selected is called "item_set" and the MBA seeks to find associations between users of these items.

IF {X, 0} THEN {0 + Y}

Probability {X, 0} is called "support", conditional probability {0 + Y} is called "confidence". The complexity of an MBA arises when exploiting large amounts of data so detailed transaction items must be available. The main difficulty of the MBA is the many rules that relate to the marketing business. Rules that have minimal support with a high level of trust can be exploited after a solution is obtained.

In financial performance analysis needs to be done impulsively. MBA analysis can provide clues to associations between items so that the main ideas can be obtained. The MBA can be used technically to uncover associations between financial aspects. The MBA works by finding a combination of characteristics that often appear in each aspect.

3) Financial Performance

Financial performance is the result or achievement that has been achieved by the company's management in carrying out its function of managing company assets effectively over a certain period [9]. Financial performance, which is a picture of the financial condition in a certain period both regarding aspects of fund raising and fund distribution, which is usually measured by indicators of capital adequacy, liquidity, and profitability [10].

Financial performance tends to be and definitely measures financial problems. Financial analysis has been very basic and general that serves to assess past

performance by means of analysis looking at the potentials [11]. Financial performance is an analysis conducted to assess the extent to which a company has carried out using the rules of financial implementation properly and correctly [12].

From the literatures that already exists, financial performance is a process or outcome that is very influential on the company, good or bad performance depends on financial analysis looking at its functions. In this study the company's performance indicators are measured from the gross profit ratio, net profit ratio, current asset ratio, debt ratio and total asset turnover.

a) *Gross Profit Ratio (GP)*

Profitability ratio that shows the relationship between gross profit and total revenue on net sales. GP is used to evaluate business operational performance.

b) *Net Profit Ratio (NP)*

The percentage of net profit is the ratio of profit after tax to net sales. NP reveals the remaining profit after all production, administrative and financing costs have been deducted from sales and income tax. NP is one of the best measures of a company's overall results, especially when combined with evaluations using working capital. The size of the NP can be seen from the timeline and compared to the business results of competitors.

c) *Current Assets Ratio (CA)*

Current ratio is a liquidity ratio that measures a company's ability to pay short-term liabilities or within a period of less than one year. CAs can provide investors and analysts with information on how companies can maximize current assets on the balance sheet to meet current debt.

d) *Debt Ratio (DR)*

DR (debt ratio) is a financial ratio that measures the level of corporate leverage. Debt ratio is the ratio of total debt to total assets, expressed in decimal or percentage terms. DR can be interpreted as a proportion of company assets that can be financed by debt.

e) *Total Assets Turnover (AT)*

Total assets turnover is an efficiency ratio that measures a company's ability to generate sales from assets by comparing net sales with the average total assets. AT shows how efficiently a company can use its assets to generate sales.

b. Data Collection

The author uses a quantitative approach with data collection techniques of four household equipment sub-sectors listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, namely: PT Chitose International, PT Kedaung Indah Can, PT Langgeng Makmur Industry and PT Integra Indocabinet.

The profile of each sample entity is explained:

Table 1: Sample 1

No.	General Information	Attribute
1.	Entity Name	Chitose International
2.	Entity Code Exchange	CINT
3.	Identification number	AA687
4.	Sector	Consumer Goods Industry
5.	Controlling shareholders	National Corporation
6.	Entity Type	Group
7.	Type of security	Stock

PT Chitose International Tbk was founded in 1979 by producing chairs with high-tech processes in manufacturing. CINT partnered strongly with a Japanese company (Chitose Mfg.Col. ,Ltd) for various types of research, testing and product improvement.

Table 2: Sample 2

No.	General Information	Attribute
1.	Entity Name	Kedaung Indah Can
2.	Entity Code Exchange	KICI
3.	Identification number	AA177
4.	Sector	Consumer Goods Industry
5.	Controlling shareholders	National Corporation
6.	Entity Type	Single
7.	Type of security	Stock

PT Kedaung Indah Can was established in 1974 which is one of the manufacturers and exporters of enamel steel cookware. In 2018 KICI is one of the largest pan producers (pans) with a production capacity of 40,000 pots per day with domestic and international markets.

Table 3: Sample 3

No.	General Information	Attribute
1.	Entity Name	Langgeng Makmur Industry
2.	Entity Code Exchange	LMPI
3.	Identification number	AA213
4.	Sector	Consumer Goods Industry

5.	Controlling shareholders	National Corporation
6.	Entity Type	Single
7.	Type of security	Stock

PT Langgeng Makmur Industry Tbk is a multinational company that produces household appliances in Sidoarjo Regency. The company was listed on the stock exchange in 1994.

Table 4: Sample 4

No.	General Information	Attribute
1.	Entity Name	Integra Indocabinet
2.	Entity Code Exchange	WOOD
3.	Identification number	AA767
4.	Sector	Consumer Goods Industry
5.	Controlling shareholders	National Corporation
6.	Entity Type	Group
7.	Type of security	Stock

PT Integra Indocabinet Tbk is engaged in the furniture and wood production industry as well as conducting import and export trading business. WOOD is a Group type entity that has seven subsidiaries with majority shareholders, PT Integra Indo Lestari (79.31%).

c. Data Collection

The research variables used to analyze company performance are:

- Gros Profit Rasio
Formula : $\frac{Gross\ Profit}{Net\ Sales}$
- Net Profit Rasio
Formula : $\frac{Net\ Profit}{Net\ Sales}$
- Current Asset Rasio
Formula : $\frac{Current\ Asset}{Current\ Liabilities}$
- Debt Rasio
Formula : $\frac{Total\ Liabilities}{Total\ Asset}$
- Total Assets Turnover
Foemula : $\frac{Net\ Sales}{Total\ Asset}$

d. Method of Analysis

The method used in this study is the CBR (Case-Based Reasoning) and MBD (Market Basket Analysis) method with the following stages [13]:

1) Retrieve

Retrieving the case that most closely resembles the relevance of the new case, the retrieval stage begins by describing some of the problems, and ends if a match is found to the previous problem with the highest level of compatibility. This section refers to the aspects of identification, initial compatibility, search and selection and execution.

2) Reuse

Reusing the knowledge and information of old cases based on the weight of the most relevant similarities into new cases, resulting in a solution where an adaptation to the new problem might be needed.

3) Revise

Revisiting the proposed solution is then tested in a real case (simulation). If needed, the solution will be improved to fit the new case.

4) Retain

Integrate new cases that have succeeded in getting a solution so that it can be used by subsequent cases that are similar to those cases. But if the solution fails, then explain the failure, improve the solution used and test it again.

Figure 1: Case-Based Reasoning Cycle

Market Basket Analysis is characterized by the presence of a large number of product items from related companies. The aim of the MBA is to capture the presence or absence of products in the concept of competitive financial performance between companies. The stages of the MBA process are as follows:

a) Load Transaction

Contains transaction data transaction id, characteristic id, and number of entities. The data shows a certain value contained in the aspects of the predicate of financial performance.

b) Edit, Transform and Load (ETL)

Process aggregation functions using Structure Query Language (SQL). The association was formed from GROUP BY and HAVING. Transform is used to rotate ExampleSet by grouping several samples from the same group into one channel. A set of attributes can then be renamed according to the specified property. Missing values in the sample can be replaced with the RMV (Replace Missing Value) operator.

c) FP-Growth

The FP-Growth operator can efficiently calculate the entire set of items from a given ExampleSet using the FP-tree data structure.

d) Create Association Rules

Make association rules that can be used to recommend items that have been trusted according to the rules.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the financial ratios of each company listed are as follows:

Table 5: Financial Statement 2017 (Case Based)

Year	Entity			
	CINT	KICI	LMPI	WOOD
2017				
Gross Profit	1.252	29	81	561
Net Sales	374	113	411	1.735
Net Profit	34	8	31	171
Current Asset	211	90	572	1.666
Current Liabilities	66	124	360	1.485
Total Liabilitas	94	58	458	1.930
Total Assets	477	149	835	3.843

*(in billions of rupiah)

The financial statement value is obtained from the analysis of the annual year report of each company in the household equipment sub sector.

Table 6: Financial Statement 2018 (New Case)

Year	Entity			
	CINT	KICI	LMPI	WOOD
2018				
Gross Profit	113	19	50	739
Net Sales	370	87	456	2.101
Net Profit	30	4	46	242
Current Asset	220	97	526	2.326
Current Liabilities	81	16	380	1.834
Total Liabilitas	103	59	456	2.138
Total Assets	491	154	787	4.588

*(in billions of rupiah)

In the financial statement for 2017 - 2018, seven items of report on the company's financial position and profit and loss are presented.

Table 7: Product Line Issuer

Issuer	Manufacturer
CINT	Furniture
KICI	Cooking ware
LMPH	Household appience (alumanium)
WOOD	Wood product

Then the method for calculating similarity is using the tversky method. Tversky method is a method in calculating similarity that is used to calculate the similarity of two objects (items) that are binary. In looking for old cases that have similarities with new cases, the concept of similarity will be used.

$$SIM(X, Y) = 1 - DIST(X, Y)$$

$$= 1 - \sqrt{\sum_1^n \delta(X_i, X_2)^2}$$

$$\delta(X_1, X_2) = \frac{|X_i - Y_i|}{|min_i - max_i|}$$

X = new case
 Y = case based
 Xi = case attribute x
 Yi = case attribute y

The results of the K most similar cases are followed by the Market Basket Analysis model:

i_{j1}		i_{jt}
$i_{(j+k-1)1}$		$i_{(j+k-1)t}$

Figure 2: FP-Tree Analysis Market Basket

The lines of each issuer are explained in table 3 that the company's market movements are in a line that is almost similar (Similiarity) which is described in figure 3 below :

Figure 3. Similiarity Product Market

PT Chitose Internasional Tbk, and PT Integra Indocabinet Tbk. Has the same sector in manufacturing furniture type processing. PT Kedaug Indah Can Tbk. And PT Langgeng Makmur Industry Tbk. Have a common sector in the processing of household appliance manufacturing.

Table 8: Chitos Internasional (CINT)

Ratio	2017 (N)	2018 (N+1)
Gross Profit	0,334808283	0,306279351
Net Profit	0,091970761	0,081133973
Current Asset	0,197877605	0,209009386
Debt	0,784668987	0,753773459
Total Assets Turnover	0,334808283	0,306279351

The financial ratio of the issuer of the CINT code is obtained by decreasing the gross profit ratio which affect the net profit value. Current assets in 2018 increased followed by a decrease in the debt ratio, but simultaneously asset turnover decrease due to the transfer of ownership and depreciation.

Table 9: Kedaug Indah Can (KICI)

Ratio	2017 (N)	2018 (N+1)
Gross Profit	0,25597157	0,216414649
Net Profit	0,070069533	0,046307908
Current Asset	0,387642665	0,38574618
Debt	0,759032978	0,564065596
Total Assets Turnover	0,25597157	0,216414649

The KICI issuers'ratio declined in gross profit and net profit. On the scale of assets in 2018 no significant changes were seen. The debt ratio decreases followed by a decrease in total assets.

Table 10: Langgeng Makmur Industry (LMPI)

Ratio	2017 (N)	2018 (N+1)
Gross Profit	0,196516248	0,109020311
Net Profit	0,075741214	0,100461123
Current Asset	0,549149768	0,579905087
Debt	0,492654683	0,579068523
Total Assets Turnover	0,196516248	0,109020311

Langgeng Makmur Industry, companies with LMPI code experienced a decrease in gross profit, but in terms of net profit increased due to the efficiency of net sales that can minimize transportation costs and sales commissions. Asset in 2018 are added as the debt ratio increases.

Table 11: Integra Indocabinet (WOOD)

Ratio	2017 (N)	2018 (N+1)
Gross Profit	0,323298582	0,351724153
Net Profit	0,098824921	0,115161898
Current Asset	0,502309903	0,466047532
Debt	0,451392465	0,457988106
Total Assets TurnOver	0,323298582	0,351724153

Integra Indocabinet shows an increase in gross profit and net profit. Assets in 2018 are reduced, debt increases and total assets simultaneously increase in the valuation of land and buildings.

Table 12: Similarity in The Performance of Furniture Issues

Ratio	CINT X_i	WOOD Y_i	2019 Similarity
Gross Profit	0,306	0,352	0,329
Net Profit	0,081	0,115	0,098
Current Asset	0,209	0,466	0,338
Debt	0,754	0,458	0,606
Total Assets Turnover	0,306	0,352	0,329

Chitose Internasioal which experienced a decrease in gross and net profit was inversely proportional to the value recorded by the issuer Integra Indocabinet. The two entities have similarities in the terms of the type of furniture market caps.

Figure 4: Issuer Furniture Performance

Overall Similarity of furniture product sales performance in 2019 in terms of value of similarity has not been able to provide an increase in valuation. This can be analyzed from the capital structure of the two entities with relatively different differences.

Table 13. Similarity in the Performance of Household Appliances Issues

Ratio	KICI X_i	LMPI Y_i	2019 Similarity
Gross Profit	0,216	0,109	0,163
Net Profit	0,046	0,100	0,073
Current Asset	0,386	0,580	0,483
Debt	0,564	0,579	0,572
Assets Turnover	0,216	0,109	0,163

Each industry has an average similarity value <0.5 so that the predicted performance in 2019 can be adjusted based on 2017 to 2018.

Figure 5 : Issuer Household Appliance Performance

Based on a case based analysis to determine the value similarity in each financial ratio, it is found that there is a strong similarity between the market share of CINT and WOOD issuers.

Stages of Market Basket Analysis

Market Basket is used to analyze associations between corporate entities by determining the set of financial performance to build association rules to obtain a recommendation reference.

Figure 6 : Market Basket Process

In the initial stage, load transactions are analyzed based on the synthetic value of the case based performance of each company. Then financial data is generated based on entity channels. Pivot tables are used so that each case based result consists of binary rows. After the pivot process, changes in financial ratios become indicators on a category scale.

Table 14: Market Basket Indeks

Entity	Profit			Asset		Dif	
	R	Sd	T	S	B	Y	N
CINT	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
KICI	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
LMPI	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
WOOD	0	0	1	0	1	0	0

Using the FP-Growth function, a set of items is determined for each entity. Set items that show financial performance which has the most dominant value. The results of the binary market basket are obtained from financial performance ratios.

Table 15: Value Probability Indeks

Rule	Confidence	LaPlace	Gain	Lift
1.	1	1	-0.50	2
2.	1	1	-0.50	2
7.	1	1	-0.25	4
8.	1	1	-0.25	4
11.	1	1	-0.25	4
12.	1	1	-0.25	4
15.	1	1	-0.25	4
16.	1	1	-0.25	4
17.	1	1	-0.25	4
18.	1	1	-0.25	4

The results of data processing using Rapidminer obtained a large number of set rules. In this study the rule is only displayed on the value of confidence and the value of LaPlace = 1 (meet the requirements). The premise value is obtained from the basketball market index and the conclusion value is obtained from the value probability index.

Table 16: Market Basket Recommendation

Rule	Premises	Conclusion
1	Hight Profit	Many assets
2	Many assets	Hight Profit
7	No differentiation	Low profit
8	Low profit	No differentiation
11	Few assets, Product differentiation	Moderate profit
12	Moderate profit	Few assets, Product differentiation
15	No differentiation	Few assets Low profit
16	Few assets, No differentiation	Low profit
17	Low profit	Few assets No differentiation
18	Few assets, Low profit	No differentiation

The final results of the basketball market calculation obtained 11 main rules that show the premise and conclusion results from the case base of the performance of household appliances sub-sector companies listed on the

Stock Exchange.

Discussion

Household appliances sub-sector companies that have high profit predicate are explained in graph 5 with rule 10 and rule 2. Companies with high profit have good product differentiation criteria and adequate company assets. Rules 1 and 9 explain the prediction scenario for companies that have large amounts of assets. The higher the asset, the more product differentiation and the increase in profit is easier to achieve.

Product differentiation is pinned on companies that have various types of product choices vary according to customer needs. If product differentiation can absorb market potential, it cannot ensure profitability. Product differentiation in household appliances sub-sector companies is also not lineary related to the amount of ownership of asset. Companies that have low profits are caused by lack of asset and insufficiency product differentiation. This was explained by the 7th and 15th Basket Market Rule.

A limitation of the results of the recommendations on the CBR and MBA methodologies is the use of new items or types of objects that are less popular which causes too high specialization in the decisions produced. CBR and MBA methods tend to ignore structures that underlie user preferences with a lack of evaluation of the decisions obtained. This study overcomes these obstacles by calculating probabilities with varying distributions to indicate a higher level of knowledge.

V. CONCLUSION

Research on the performance of the issuers of the household appliances subsector industry with the Case Based Reasoning and Market Basket Analysis approach obtained the following conclusions: The similiarity value of the case based results to predict the company's financial performance in 2019 can be explained using five ratio indicators. The results of the distribution of financial performance can provide a system of recommendations in the form of identification of companies with high profits, asset management, product differentiation and explain the characteristics of companies with low profits.

VI. SUGGESTION

Researchers suggest to develop a financial-based recommendation system to predict the company's performance in the coming year. The flow of financial ratio analysis can be processed into data mining to provide recommendations to the public in reaching investment access on the Stock Exchange.

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A Novel Study for Spatio-Temporal Query Processing using Privacy Preservation

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Abstract-The prevailing infrastructure of ubiquitous computing paradigm on the one hand making significant development for integrating technology in the daily life but on the other hand raising concerns for privacy and confidentiality. As Location based services (LBS) equip users to query information specific to a location with respect to temporal and spatial factors thus LBS put under extreme criticism when it comes to location privacy and user confidentiality. Here in this paper we are addressing the significance of our proposed scheme, a query processing architecture for privacy preservation in LBS, by providing flexible and efficient LBS model to ensure accurate and qualitative result set by employing some indexing scheme at location anonymizer as well as by Identifying possible adversary attacks to breach user privacy in the previous work with respect to location privacy and query privacy. Realizing the need for a unanimous query processing model which can operate in centralized as well as distributed environment, also flexible enough to provide privacy for public queries (snapshot/continuous) as well as private queries (snapshot/continuous) for public and private locations. Finally we will quantify the benefits of our approach using sampled results through experiments that the proposed cloaking algorithm is scalable, efficient and robust to support anonymity irrespective of scale of user queries in real time scenario.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ubiquitous computing is the method of enhancing computer use by making many computers available throughout the physical environment, but making them effectively invisible to the user. LBS play a pivotal role in ubiquitous computing. Due to the proliferation of location based devices, prolific growth has been made to expand the huge base of LBS. For example, you might have observed the abrupt turning up of cabs at the stand since they have been using GPS devices, one of the most recent applications of LBS to track passengers and routes where the mobile user is willing to reveal his or her location. On the other hand, mobile users want to access LBS to locate nearest hospital without revealing his or her location as per privacy concern. Other examples include real time traffic congestion monitoring, detailed directions, integrated search results on dynamic maps, satellite imagery, location-based advertisements and etc. In location-based applications, location-based database server is responsible to process location-based query triggered by user with respect to the revealed spatial information [12]. In fact this authoritative location-based database server is untrusted primarily relying on the revealed user location, thereby raising critical concerns related to privacy and security of the registered users. In order to exploit location-based services, users have to compromise their privacy with such untrusted location-based database servers or simply ensure their privacy by limiting the quality of location-based services. Thus an adversary may access sensitive information related to user by breaching the security of untrusted location-based server or may reveal the user information by examining trends of different publicly available location-based data from such untrusted applications. In order to build up the confidence of users in location based services, there is a pressing need to introduce such privacy preserving models that not only mitigate the privacy and security threats but also provide efficient and scalable computing mechanism. In this regard several cloaking algorithms have been proposed by research community to preserve user privacy for motivating users towards location based services [9]. In existing approaches [3, 2, 17, 20, 8], user is supposed to indicate his/her privacy requirement in terms of K-anonymity model which is then blurred into a spatial region by

cloaking algorithm. Thus the efficiency of cloaking algorithm has direct impact on the characteristics of privacy preservation model with respect to quality, flexibility and privacy.

Following are the shortcomings that motivated us for our contribution for privacy preservation towards location-based services. (i) Existing approaches employ cloaking algorithms on inefficient data structure such as hierarchical data structure [17] which supposed to exhibit poor performance in real time scenario when the scale and speed of mobile users are changed vigorously. (ii) Centralized anonymizer [17] subjects to bottleneck for the overall system in the presence of poor data structure such anonymizer can be compromised or yield dithered computing performance if the underlying data structure is not flexible. (iii) Irrespective of being static or dynamic model several approaches lack efficiency in the absence of particular data indexing model.

Our motivation to conduct this research study is to present a well balanced query processing architecture which is efficient as well as privacy aware while the focus of existing approaches seems to skew towards privacy irrespective of overall efficiency of privacy preservation model. Our contribution made in this paper can be summarized as follows:

- Deploying R-tree based indexing scheme for location anonymizer to make best use of available resources i.e. memory and processing time
- Development of efficient cloaking algorithm to evaluate optimized result set in response to user queries
- Performance analysis of conducted experiments' to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithms

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section 2 presents related work in the area of LBS with respect to privacy preservation. Section 3 outlines the architecture of location anonymizer. Cloaking algorithm along with different practical scenarios is discussed in section 4. In section 5, we describe the performance evaluation of our proposed cloaking algorithm in contrast with other existing approaches. Finally, we conclude our work in section 6.

II. RELATED WORK

The K-anonymity model [18] is one of the premier models in the data privacy domain which have influenced research community unanimously. In the most general sense, K-anonymity model addresses the concern of privacy when it comes to release a version of private data by data holder for practical usage with some scientific assurance that privacy of individuals cannot be compromised by matching similar trends of different version of data. L. Sweeney [20] defines K-anonymity as : A relation is said to be Kanonymous provided each record in the relation is indistinguishable from at least K-1 other records with respect to a set of quasi-identifier attributes. In the context of Location Based services, K-anonymity model ensures the privacy of mobile users by making their locations indistinguishable among at least other K-1 users. The synergy of K-anonymity model with spatio-temporal cloaking [9] is one of the open debates among researchers interested in emerging privacy preservation models. Thus K-anonymity is one of the crucial requirements for flexible and efficient location-based query processing model [3] as widely discussed in Clique- Cloak algorithm [2], spatio-temporal cloaking algorithm [9] and peer-to-peer spatial cloaking algorithm [5]. The Clique-Cloak algorithm [2] can only accommodate few users with limited K-anonymity requirements due to computation overhead and also suffer from topographical adversary attacks. The spatio-temporal cloaking [9] technique fails when it comes to scalability since this technique is optimized to track each single movement individually. The peer-to-peer spatial cloaking algorithm [5] finds K-1 NN(Nearest Neighbour) of query source but this approach suffers from "center-of-ASR" attack. Mokbel et al [6] presents algorithm for privacy preservation in scenarios where user can reveal its location for public queries while can also hide both location and query for private query at private location. The addressed algorithm works on snapshot queries as well as continues

queries. The significant part of this work is the identification of centralized location anonymizer for location-based services implying a hierarchical data structure which is supposed to be invulnerable to adversary attacks such as query sampling for snapshot queries and query tracking for continuous queries. This scheme is subjected to poor performance in the presence of hierarchical data structure in real time scenario and also proposed cloaking algorithm fails to defend maximum movement boundary attack and public queries versus private queries attack. Prive [8], a distributed system for query anonymization in LBS, comes with HilbASR algorithm. Prive only considers snapshot queries, lack of support for continuous queries and also static version of HilbASR lacks flexibility in terms of data indexing model. Since our approach is quite similar as that of Casper, query processing paradigm discussed in Mokbel et al [16], which relies on third-party middleware to cloak user locations. This framework is suffered from centralized architecture as it can be bottleneck for the overall system or may raise a concern for single point of failure. The third-party middleware can also be compromised or may subject to ban for disclosing sensitive information such as the case of Napster as deploying centralized architecture. Apart from that it requires user to continuously report anonymizer

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system architecture has three main components: the mobile user, the location anonymizer and the location based database server. The mobile user interacts with the system by registering privacy profile [7] which specifies the typical privacy requirement of user with respect to the K-anonymity (K) and the minimum area (δ). K-anonymous parameter of privacy profile simply indicates that among how many other users the particular mobile user does not want to be distinguishable, while specifies desired coverage of the cloaked spatial region. Larger values of and results in restrictive privacy thereby degrading quality of service. Different privacy profiles can be set by mobile users to meet the desired privacy level at any time. Next step for mobile users is to report their spatial location and/or spatial query to the location anonymizer. The location anonymizer, after receiving location updates from mobile users, employs spatial cloaking technique to blur the users location and/or queries into cloaked spatial region as per specification of privacy profile. The blurred cloaked spatial region is then sent to the location-based database server which is spatially tuned to deal with the spatial cloaked region instead of exact resultset rather than actual resultset is computed according to cloaked spatial region. The candidate resultset is then returned to the mobile user through location anonymizer which previously computed the blurred spatial region based on the privacy profile, eventually mobile user who initiated the query is responsible to extract actual result from the candidate resultset. The efficiency and accuracy of proposed system directly influenced by data structure scheme and cloaking algorithm Embedded in the core of system i.e. the location anonymizer and the strictness of privacy profile. In the next section, we will discuss how our proposed location anonymizer can really play its part to drive the overall system efficiently and accurately as far as underlying data indexing and cloaking algorithm is concerned. On the other hand, the strictness of privacy profile simply puts operational trade-off between the level of privacy and the QoS (Quality of Service) which is solely manifested by the mobile user.

IV. LOCATION ANONYMIZER

The location anonymizer is a trusted third party that acts as the middleware between mobile users and back-end location-based database server. The location anonymizer incrementally keeps track the number of users residing in The system and also consistently keep track of continuous movement of mobile users. Therefore, a key question for Developing location anonymizer is: How accurate, scalable and efficient is the cloaking mechanism employed by location anonymizer? In order to address this primary concern for location anonymizer, we propose for the deployment of an indexing scheme to address mobile users efficiently and effectively. The fundamental assumption used for designing efficient location anonymizer is that the spatial datasets are indexed by the structures of R-tree family. R-tree and its variants [11] are considered excellent choices for indexing a range of spatial data such as

points, line segments, rectangles, polygons and so forth and have already been deployed commercially (Informix and Oracle). The R-tree [10] is one of the most popular approaches for spatial access methods i.e., for indexing multi-dimensional information such as (x,y) coordinates of geographical data. R-tree is hierarchical in nature where high level node is termed as MBR (minimum bounding rectangle) that supposed to enclose a set of child MBRs at the next level in hierarchy except the lowest level where data objects are stored within the MBRs as depicted. Root node represents the coverage of whole space of system and then the overall system space is hierarchically decomposed. Until now a number of R-tree variants [15] have been developed by the research community [19, 4, 13, 14, 1] as far as optimized performance of this promising indexing scheme for real-world data is concerned. R+ trees [19], a dynamic index for spatial access methods, differ from conventional R-tree by avoiding overlapping of internal nodes by inserting an object into multiple leaves thereby improving performance of point query since all spatial regions are covered by at most one node as well as fewer path traversal. Beckmann et al. [4] proposed the R*-tree which is more efficient in insertion and space utilization than the R-tree based on force-reinserted technique to avoid the overhead of splitting a full node. The Hilbert R-tree [13], which uses a Hilbert space filling curve outperforms the R*-tree by giving a better space localization. SR-tree "Sphere/Rectangle-tree" [14], an index structure for high-dimensional nearest neighbor queries, differs from other R-tree variants by combining utilization of bounding spheres and bounding rectangles thus showing improved performance on nearest neighbor queries by reducing both the volume and the diameter of regions. Conventional R-tree does not promise good worst-case performance but performing well when it comes to real-world data. The Priority R-Tree [1] is one of the efficient R-tree variants and is at the same time worst-case optimal. Irrespective of different R-tree variants, in our proposed model the whole space can be decomposed into several spatial regions. The root of R-tree will represent the whole projected space. Each entry within a leaf node stores two pieces of information related to an element i.e. (i) Bounding box identifier of that element (ii) Number of users in corresponding bounding box. When a mobile user is registered in the system with some unique identifier and privacy profile, a hash table is maintained to store an entry of form (uid,prf,bid) where uid is the user id, prf is user defined privacy profile and bid is the bounding box identifier for bounding box holding that particular user. Any of existing R-tree scheme can be employed to search, insert and delete elements in the data structure. One of the crucial aspect of location-based application is to maintain the mobile user updates as such applications tend to operate in highly dynamic environment thus requires flexible data structure for frequent updates. When a mobile user changes its location, location update is sent to location anonymizer in the form (uid,x,y) where uid is the user identifier, x and y are new spatial coordinates after location update. In order to get new bounding box for the updated location of user, location anonymizer simply applies hash function $h(x,y)$. Now depending on the resulting bounding box, If it matches with the previous bounding box then location anonymizer will not do any processing at all. In case if it does not match with the previous bounding box then location anonymizer performs three operations i.e. updating new bounding box, incrementing user in new bounding box and decrementing user in old bounding box. If a new user is registered, a new entry will be marked in hash table and then marked in R-tree by insertion procedure. If a user quits the system then its corresponding entry in hash table is deleted and then removed from R-tree by deletion procedure.

IV. CONCLUSION

The horizon of LBS is being diminished by the raising concerns for privacy and confidentiality. This paper presents a novel query processing architecture for privacy preservation which can be deployed to motivate mobile users towards LBS without compromising privacy as well as quality through efficient and robust cloaking algorithm. Existing privacy techniques in LBS such as Casper [16] and Prive [8] is suffered by adversary attacks [6], query tracking [6], query sampling [6] and maximum movement boundary attack. Apart from that performance of these existing schemes can further be improved by implying indexing technique such as R-tree. Our proposed scheme can be deployed in centralized as well as distributed environment and is free from all existing adversary attacks by devising robust, efficient and flexible cloaking algorithm for privacy *preservation*.

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The Future of E-Government: From One Stop Shop to No Stop Shop solution

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Abstract— Purpose: The purpose of this study was to evaluate the potential trends and issues faced in the development and adoption of e-government systems and the impact this will have on the future of e-government. The aim was to evaluate the progression of e-government systems from the one-stop-model characterized by offering government services online to a no-stop-model characterized by innovative governance. This will be marked by the development of future software development model for e-government systems.

Methods: An online desk research was conducted to identify secondary sources that outline the trends and issues faced by e-government systems. This will serve to inform any unmet needs and aspirations with existing models as well as opportunities and threats that should be anticipated in the design of e-government software models.

Findings: The research identified that there is an overarching need to enhance the participation and integration of public service delivery to make the process seamless, personalized, and proactive to future trends, opportunities, and threats. Hence, feature driven model is presented as an effective model to spark the development to a no-stop-shop model for e-government systems from the prevalent one-stop-shop model.

Conclusion: While there is a need for e-government systems to meet the functional objectives regarding offering public services, there is a need for the incorporated software model to future-proof the resultant e-government system to foreseeable and unforeseeable opportunities and threats.

Keywords: citizens, e-government, no-stop-shop, one-stop-shop, public services.

I. INTRODUCTION

Citizens and businesses alike will often interact with the government to receive public services. This is because, it is the mandate of the government to provide these services under the social contract upon which the premise of the government is founded upon. However, it is key to note that the delivery of these services is reliant on the collection and processing of data by the government [1]. Throughout time, this process has been continually streamlined especially with the adoption of technological advancements giving rise to e-government as a way to enhance the efficiency of public service delivery.

While there is no standard definition of e-government, the United Nations describes e-government as the utilization of ICTs to effectively and efficiently deliver public services to both citizens and businesses. However, it is key to note that it is only recently that e-government has entailed the utilization of ICTs since traditionally, e-government was overly focused on the provision of public services online. As such, e-government has evolved from being constrained to the perception of “online government services” to “innovation governance” marked by increased interactions and engagement between the government and the businesses and citizenry [2]. This outlines the aim of this paper, through the evaluation of the prevalent issues and trends and how this will influence the future of e-government a feature-driven software development model will be suggested as an effective and efficient way to drive the transition of e-government from a one-stop-shop to a no-stop-shop model.

The paper will be structured as follows; section 2 will present past literature relevant to the research topic. Section 3 will detail the implemented research design. Section 4 will then present a proposed model and the feature-driven model and how it aids in the transition from a one-stop-shop to a no-stop-shop. Section 5 will discuss how the new model will enhance e-government systems, especially, collection of requisite information and the subsequent delivery of a service. This will be achieved by mainly contextualizing it with existing research and models. Finally, section 6 will bring together all conclusions arrived at by the research inquiry.

II. BACKGROUND

According to [3] since the conceptualization of e-government in the 1990s, it has transformed public administration both from a cultural and organizational stance. This is because, the introduction of ICT and digital age technologies transformed the environment to an extent that it necessitated the governance systems to respond and evolve with this change [3]. It is important to note that the relationships and interactions between agents will usually influence the complex behavior in a system. With regard to this, it is posited that the association between ICT and government is co-evolutionary in that they both interact in a dynamic and changing environment.

From a public administration stance, the volatility of the environment and its evolutionary nature is evidenced by the

continued need for reforms at different levels of society. This understanding is furthered by [4] who outlines that the complexity of public administration is rooted in the realities of public administration. That is, it is carried out by numerous agencies and departments, it requires legislation and operating procedures outlined, as well as the continued adoption of requisite technologies. The co-evolutionary nature of both ICT and governance is then accurately described by [5] who outline that the existence of different forms and areas for the adoption of ICT have resulted in an increase in the variety of technologies with the capacity to further online administration. Governance then has to improve by adopting these technologies.

However, given the diversity of the areas and forms of application, it should be noted that the user of the platform determines the adoption and satisfaction of an e-government system. This is because, it is aimed at aiding every citizen to meet their human development needs. By extension, the design and adoption of e-government systems should be guided by an understanding of the needs of all public segments.

A. E-government models

Reference by [4] posit that online service delivery is at the core of e-government initiatives. Therefore, the development and deployment of systems that make this possible become a key priority. It is this that sets credence for the evaluation of methodologies, platforms and tools utilized in the e-government systems’ software development process. As a result, several models have traditionally been used to create and develop e-government systems which offers insight into the steps of implementation used in developing the e-government system, and with it the aim of the system for public administration [6]. The first model, Layne and Lee, features four stages with the underlying aim being the creation of an integrated information base to bring about an integration of processes and functions on different levels of government. Hence, the transfer of these services to online channels creates a one-stop-shop model for accessing public services.

The next model, referred by [7] adds interactivity to the integrated information base. This not only allows for the public to receive government services but to also request them as they can now contact governmental officials and organizations online [6]. The next model, UN's (2001), advocates for public administration and its services to be accessed and provided seamlessly which necessitates all government agencies and departments function as a single and universal presence where citizens and other stakeholders access all kinds of services instantly and conveniently through one portal. In addition to ensuring the integration of all services, the Model of [8] introduces the participation phase that allows for voting services to be offered online and also allowing the public to post comments online [6]. Finally, the model of Wescott (2001) proposes a six-stage model that is an improvement from the previous as it allows for a joined-up government. Whereby, in addition to accessing all services on a web portal this model outlines that services and information are integrated to an extent that a user only identifies with the received services as they may

not necessarily know the involved government agency or department.

TABLE 1: FIVE MODELS OF E-GOVERNMENT

MODELS	PHASE 1	PHASE 2	PHASE 3	PHASE 4	PHASE 5	PHASE 6
Layne and Lee (2001)		Catalogue	Transaction	Vertical Integration	Horizontal Integration	
Baum and Di Maio (2000)	The Web Presence	Interaction	Transaction	Transformation		
UN's (2001)	Emerging Presence Web	Enhanced Presence	Interactive	Transaction Government	Seamless	
Hiller and Belanger (2001)		Information Dissemination	Two-way Communication	Transaction	Integration	Participation
Wescott (2001)	Email and Internal Work	Enabled Information Access to Information for Organizations and the Public	Two-way Communication	Exchange of Value	Digital Democracy	Joined-up Government

Source: Reference by [6]

B. The one-stop-shop model

Reference [9] outline that e-government is an attempt at modernizing public administration with the online one-stop-government being the first step on how that is achieved. This form of e-government is characterized by the integration of all public services to allow citizens and businesses to access public services from a single point even if the services are delivered by different departments or authorities. Reference by [1] defines “who asserts that without such a model, every department and authority would be contacted independently with a citizen or business having to distribute the needed data to every department or authority”. Instead, this information is submitted to a single access point. Hence, from the perspective of a citizen, the one-stop-shop model is an integration of public services. On the other hand, the government perceives it as interconnectedness and interoperability of IT systems across its different agencies and departments.

However, while this is a key development its effectiveness and efficiency are significantly impacted by its reliance on forms and its reactivity. With regards to forms, while they are the primary interface for collecting information to deliver a service, they negatively impact the overall service delivery experience. This is because, filling the forms is cumbersome, repetitive whilst there is a risk of low comprehensibility. On the other hand, the reactivity of this model is rooted in the fact that service delivery is triggered by a citizen or a business and in each engagement, citizens will need to provide data. E-government models usually have five steps in common:

1. Publication of information on websites.
2. Communication with citizens via electronic channels.
3. Offering transaction services online.
4. Delivery of integrated e-government services.
5. E-Participation of citizens in decision making.

As one stop shops are commonly used, there are no proposals for possible extensions for these phased models. Therefore, to fill this gap the next step for governments is the transition from a one-stop shop to a no-stop shop. For a no stop-shop model to be designed, implemented, and assessed the three steps

approach has been taken.

The no-stop-shop-model is therefore presented as a natural solution to problems faced by the one-stop-shop model. That is, by transitioning from no-form service delivery towards proactive and ultimately predictive service delivery, it is possible to autonomously offer services and information that is both personalized and relevant to a citizen's life circumstances. Hence, for a no-stop-shop model service delivery is triggered by a life event occurrence or in anticipation of the occurrence of a life event. In either case, no request of a public service is made and by extension, it means no form is required to be filled before these services are received. Instead, citizens and businesses alike receive them as recommendations and features personalized to the prevalent life realities.

III. METHODS

This research inquiry relied on secondary sources to identify the trends and issues for e-government systems and the development process, and as a result infer the future of e-government. That is, through online desk research, this research identified journal articles, web articles, books, government publications among other sources to determine user-level factors that influence the development and adoption of e-government systems. This was followed by the determination of gaps that a future software development model should address which led to the conceptualization of a model.

A. *An Approach to No-Stop-Shop*

Firstly, the first draft of the phase model based in the research context is built on an established Theory of the phase and related work on forms, constructive government, and data integration. The stage model is refined iteratively in discussions in a group of four researchers.

Second, two semi-structured interviews were conducted. The aim of the interviews was to provide an initial insight into the validity and scale of the model, the government's current strategy for implementing a no-stop shop and the anticipated challenges and opportunities for implementing a no-stop shop.

Third, a number of further interviews were conducted with practitioners to sharpen the model and to validate its face and gain initial insights into the possible problems which would impede progress towards a 'no-stop-shop' for further understanding of the context.

There are three dimensions of no-stop shop. First "Integration of Data Collection" refers to and managing forms. Citizens benefit from an integrated data collection because information must be submitted exclusively to a single entity and the repeated entry of same information in various forms is not necessary. Governments also benefits from integrated data collection by increasing the data quality and decreased effort to manage forms that result from a reduced additional form length. It should, however, be stored regardless of how the data reaches the government. So, the second stage refers to "Integration of Data Storage". This dimension addresses data processing within and through governments.

For two reasons, an integrated data storage is useful: Firstly, it allows removal of forms or decreases the complexity of a form when it is not possible to fully remove them. Secondly, the incorporation of data storage is a crucial third-dimensional facilitator that reflects on how data are used. In particular it enables analysis of proactive services which are activated by the government and predictive services before the fact, after the fact, and by the administration. This will make possible proactive and predictive service delivery which is the highest point on the third dimension. Lastly the third dimension "Purpose of Data Use" is used which refers to the use of stored and organized data. These dimensions are used to provide insights into how government service delivery can progress through the stages "One-Stop-Shop", "Limited No-Stop-Shop" and "No-Stop-Shop". The "No-Stop Shop" is characterized for the proactive and predictive delivery of the service and is characterized as an extension of "One-Stop Shop." This results in the delivery of public services without any intervention taken by the citizen. We propose an intermediary stage called the "Limited No-Stop-Shop" before enforcing the final No-Stop-Shop which still depends on forms. During this point, the administration carries out proactive or predictive delivery, thereby reducing the acts the citizen carries out.

To conclude, while the objective of a 'one-stop shop' is to decrease the number of forms by integration of the front end, a 'no-stop shop' seeks to avoid an exchange of information between the people and the government. The "one stop shop" idea considers the form as a central component of the provision of government services and acts as the sole touch point for citizens — the "no stop shop" removes this point of contact and therefore all aspects of the provision of state services.

The No-Stop shop uses two ways, for this reason, to fulfil the two purposes of forms and serve as alternatives, integrated storage of data to make available all the data needed and a constructive, predictive model to predict whether a citizen requires a service before a citizen asks for a service. It does not contribute to "No-Shop" just supporting one of the two: If missing information is required or the customer has to send a service delivery form.

B. *Proposed model*

By relying on agile development, feature-driven development was identified as the best approach to build a proactive and predictive system and by evaluating the available digital technological capabilities and existing frameworks a conceptual model on how these capabilities can be capitalized on to address the existing gaps with the prevalent models was presented. Past literature was also used to support how the proposed feature-driven e-government model was aligned with the future of e-government both in terms of development and utilization, specifically, the advancement from a one-stop-shop model to a no-stop-shop model for public service delivery.

First, it is key to outlined that FDD is an agile development approach and as such, its software development approach is grounded on iterative development. What is more, as a basic

requirement, the scope and requirements have to be laid down before the development process. Central to agile development, the number of iterations, duration and scope of each are also defined in advance. Finally, it should be noted that each iteration will involve a team that goes through the full software development lifecycle before a working product can be developed and demonstrated.

Lynn (2021) posits that FDD is innately customer-centric, iterative and incremental that is focused on delivering tangible results often and efficiently. By reducing both confusion and rework, it becomes superior model as the project can be regularly updated and errors can be identified quickly. It makes it ideal for long-term and complex projects. This grounds the rationale behind using FDD as the underlying model. That is, the complexity is due to the manner that public services are delivered, by different agencies and departments whereas the longevity of development is as a result of the co-evolutionary nature shared by ICT technologies and governance mechanisms. FDD was chosen because of its customer-centrism which is important since both the adoption and satisfaction of e-government systems is determined by the end-user. Moreover, since flexibility and proactivity are what are needed to improve e-government while enhancing overall alignment future trends and capacity to respond to the changing needs and aspirations of the citizenry, a feature-driven approach is effective in ingraining these competencies in e-government systems.

Therefore, the development phases will be structured as iterations which means their design and development will follow the steps set out by FDD, these are, gathering data, developing the overall model, building a feature list, planning by feature, designing by feature and finally, building by feature.

Figure 1: Feature Driven Development Phases

- Developing an overall model – This step will involve detailing the problem the software development project should solve. In addition to aiding in the definition of context and scope for the system, it serves as an outline for the entire phase.
- Building a feature list – This step will evaluate the functional value of the e-government at every phase to determine the flexibility and proactivity gaps. This will inform the features that should be introduced at each phase.
- Planning by feature – From the identified features, this will entail determining the needed resources to actualize each phase.
- Designing by feature – In this step, different stakeholders will be involved to determine the technical and framework specifics as well as the feature priorities for every phase.
- Building by feature – In this final step, all the needed items that support the design are implemented, these are, the user interface, technical components, and a module for each phase is

made available for testing and approval.

C. Stages

Overall, the aim of the model is to ensure the transition of e-government from its current one-stop-shop and embrace a no-stop-shop model. However, considering the complexity of governance and the changing nature of public administration, several changes have to be made at different levels to create an enabling environment for the needed competencies to be introduced and others enhanced. As aforementioned, each stage after requirement definition will be considered an iterative stage, and as a result, their development will take on an FDD approach by adhering to the steps. Therefore, the overall model is driven by the objective of not only making the government suggest services but it goes on to become an initiator of a public service. For instance, the government can start rolling out the pension funds when one gets to the legal retirement age. This is without the citizen having to ask for the pension funds. Hence, each phase will focus on how to enhance its proactive and predictive capacity and how to continually enhance it.

PHASE	DESCRIPTION
Requirement definition	This phase will require developing an understanding of the needs and aspirations of businesses, citizens, and communities within a jurisdiction. This will underly the development process whereby, the objectives of the system will be aligned with these needs and aspirations as well as the human development needs.
Collaborative design and development	Collaborative involvement of representatives from the constituent groups will be important to evaluate the usability, efficiency, and effectiveness of the system. This is aimed at ensuring information and service gaps are effectively addressed.
Joined up government	This will focus on ensuring the vertical and horizontal integration of government departments, agencies, and functions to a single, interactive and seamless system.
Monitoring and participation	This will allow for democratic, transactional interaction with the government in its entirety. It shall allow for feedback on service delivery among other aspects of the e-government system to inform future development/improvement efforts.

IV. DISCUSSION AND RECOMANDATIONS

As outlined by [10] and [11] digital technology are important in the development of smart societies which are characterized by the thoughtful deployment of digital technologies by the government to improve the welfare of citizens, economic stability, and institutional effectiveness. In this regard, technology becomes an avenue to attain these objectives. Reference [12] goes on to outline that government leaders are increasingly being evaluated with regards to the benefits they create for the constituents, who comprise citizens, communities, and businesses. Just like typical clients, these groups expect top performance and efficiency, the delivery of better service and results, public trust, and appropriate accountability. When this is coupled up with the fact that novel aspirations of citizens are resulting in novel demands on governments around the world, key among them being the need for transparency, efficiency, and enhanced performance [12], [11].

Therefore, the feature-driven model is uniquely aligned to result in the development of a smart society. By imbuing public service delivery with the capacity to autonomously offer government services proactively and predictively, this will enhance overall welfare of citizens and businesses. Finally, as [6] asserts that most governments are interested in e-government initiatives to ensure efficient provision of public services, enhance engagement between citizens and the state, ensure the integrity of information between government agencies. This model will allow for this since the outcome is a flexible system capable of allowing for the quick adaptation to the changing needs and social realities. Hence, as aforementioned earlier, while service delivery has traditionally been subsequent to the collection of information, the feature-driven model will serve to do away with the necessity of information collection, instead, a record is made existent autonomously following one's birth and is continuously updated both autonomously and from the different points of contact that will exist between an individual and the government.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper aimed to evaluate the potential trends and issues of e-government and their influence on the future of e-government, specifically how the one-stop model will evolve towards a no stop model. We propose a model stage where we will create a digital form in which the citizens will get access only to their concerned feature whereas the government will have access to their required information. The purpose of introducing this model is to avoid the hassle of multiple forms as well as provide a distinction between government and citizen's related data in a single database. The form will be customizable therefore can be transformed according to the requirements of the offered services. Since the access will be given according to the needs of the user, boundaries for the dimensions will be created.

The proposed feature-driven model allows for this progression as it sets out a path how e-government systems should be designed to ensure flexibility and proactivity is an inherent competence. The importance of this is that the resultant system can be continually tweaked to fit the changing needs and aspirations as well as the prevalent social realities. Therefore, as the opportunities for the implementation of ICT in governance continue to evolve and the needs and aspirations of constituents continue to change, an inherent need to transcend the provision of public services as a central premise for e-governments and adopt a more active role in the life of constituents is presented. To attain this, there is a need to enhance an understanding of the constituents and personalize service delivery which ought to direct the design and development of e-government systems.

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Intelligent Software Defined Energy Management System for IoT networks

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Abstract— Recently, ubiquitous computing gained huge advances after internet of things (IoT) has become an essential ecosystem. The combination of high energy consumption and difficulty in timely energy generation, substitution and redistribution present real challenges currently. This paper presents an energy management solution consisting of a combination of a networked energy harvesters, real-time energy consumption monitoring, and energy storage with an intelligent distribution system. The proposed solution is based on the use of a redundant battery that is always kept at a standby energy level and recharged directly from a harvester or a centralized energy storage. The management of consumption and recharging is based on the push-pull hysteresis theory concepts. The proposed system features timely monitor, tracking and controlling power consumption in both the sensor and harvest networks during the entire operation from switching ON, sensing, processing, and communication. The entire system is modeled and simulated using OMNET++ according to different wireless sensor networks technologies. It was confirmed via performing a variety of simulation experiments that the proposed solution remarkably enhanced overall system as well as device power consumption. Moreover, it showed advancement in synchronization, energy management and distribution process, adaptation of communication protocols, controllability, and lifetime accordingly.

Keywords- Energy harvesting, Energy management, Internet of Things, Sensor Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the evolution of communication technologies, the new generation of wireless networks aims to create an integration between all technologies that go beyond the concept of the internet of things (IoT) to ubiquitous networking where all devices can adapt seamlessly to communicate without any concerns regarding the technologies utilized. Most of the devices engaged in the IoT or ubiquitous networking are low-power devices that require monitoring and control in order to optimize power consumption, thus overcoming limited power constraint. Energy harvesters contribute to solving the problem of power consumption in low power devices. Energy controllers play a crucial role in the sensor network energy to maintain balance between sensor nodes in consumption and updating the route in case of failure of any node. The

synchronization process of all network devices is one of the central station devices responsibilities. This is to keep the data load balanced between the sensors and controlled by the central station based on the energy level advertised by the node. In addition to improving the performance of the network, minimizing cost as well as optimizing energy use. Therefore, several challenges have been detected regarding communication research. [1]

In ubiquitous networking, there are different technologies such as Wi-Fi that are commonly used due to the diversity of standards that allow the sensor networks to deal with different environments and requirements. Furthermore, ZigBee is another technology utilized, it is based on IEEE 802.15.4 standard model and supports Low-Rate Wireless Networks where short-range operation, low data rate, energy efficiency, and low cost are deployed.

Tracking and analyzing the performance of networks is actually a high cost, as most networks include hundreds of nodes with different technologies and protocols. Using simulation networks tool became a brilliant and suitable solution to track and analyze performance. Many simulations appeared in the past years, such as NS2, NS3, OPNET and OMNET++. There are many different simulators, nonetheless, OMNET++ comes at the top of the recommended simulation environment because it is an open source, component-based simulator, a friendly GUI and an embeddable simulation kernel.

This paper proposes a system model to optimize and enhance energy consumption in IoT networks. In order to improve power consumption over time and harvest cycle in the IoT sensor network. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: related work is represented in Section II and in Section III introduces the proposed model. Section IV, discusses the simulation setup while Section V deals with the discussion of results, and finally Section VI concludes all the work performed to achieve the optimization.

II. RELATED WORK

Ubiquitous networks face multiple challenges at different levels to meet the required efficiency and performance, for instance; handover and seamless communication between technologies and reliability, which are major challenges to ensure that all messages from the nodes reach the controllers or the gateway correctly in the shortest time and path with the minimum power consumption. Ubiquitous networking aims to objectify all things around to make things connected and controlled.

Ubiquitous networking contains many types of smart networks such as Personal Area Network (PAN). It works by injecting or attaching tiny sensor devices into the human body and monitoring all changes as well as updates. All this illustrates the importance and extensive role of the wireless sensors in life. sensor node contains its network stack as shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1 Sensor Node Representation in a Network.

The most commonly used nowadays are IEEE802.11 and IEEE802.15.4 since they support the low power devices required in IoT.

Wi-Fi represents the IEEE 802.11 standard designed to provide an internet connection to users at broadband speed. It may operate in a structure mode through an access point (AP) or AdHoc mode. It starts working by scanning the available channels to check the availability of adding more nodes to the network.

Zigbee comes from the IEEE 802.15.4 standard model, and is designed to support Low-Rate Wireless Networks where short-range operation, low data rate, energy efficiency, and low cost, operating at 2.4GHz ISM band and defining 16 channels. It consists of the physical layer and MAC address. Respectively, the first layer implements the main functions and specifications, whereas the second layer is responsible for the data transfer and management modes [2][3].

IPv6 is promising for IoT networks, increasing (MTU) from 576 to 1280 bytes. It covers an address space of 2¹²⁸ and 3.4*10³⁸ unique addresses. This should be enough for Internet to scale even with the rabid spread of the Internet of Things. On the contrary, it takes more time and power to perform due to the change in header and the stack. [4]. Fig.2 shows different representations of network stacks.

Fig.2 Network stacks.

A priority to find a solution to compromise between the advantage of the richness of ipv6 and low power devices. The result is 6LoWPAN stack, which is an intermediate layer between MAC and Network layer to support the adaption process. IETF works on 6lowPAN using IEEE802.15.4 which supports 127 Bytes as the maximum frame size. Consequently, Fragmentation and reassembling should be applied since the minimum MTU of ipv6 is 1280 Bytes. [5]

The simulation environment is an important part of the research, as is the selection of a proper simulation tool that fulfils the network environment requirements. Most simulators nowadays are discrete and event-based, therefore it is easier to extract the desire information in order to select a proper simulator, the programming language used, compatibility between nodes and protocols, as well as supporting documentations must be taken in account, especially when is open source.

OMNET++ is an open source based on C++, mainly used for educational purposes. It has a large community developing many frameworks for continuous enhancement and adding more modules to be supported like the INET framework. [6].

TABLE I - MERITS AND DEMERITS OF NETWORK SIMULATION TOOLS.

Name	Pro	Con
NS-2	- Popular. - Numerous protocols. - Expandable.	- Only 802.11 and TDMA. - No GUI. - Not large number of nodes
NS-3	- numerous libraries - expandable in C++ - wireless networks	- no computability with NS2.
OMNET++	- scalable. - expandable in C++ - Support GUI - simulate power consumption problems in WSNs	- limited protocols - incompatibility between models

After comparing 3 simulators in TABLE I, OMNET++ is the most suitable for the network scenarios in the proposed model.

In OMNET++, the network model is specified via Network Description Language (NED). NED files are not directly used; however, they are translated into C++ codes by the NED

compiler, then compiled by the C++ compiler and linked into the simulation executable as shown in Fig.3

Fig.3 The simulation process in OMNeT++.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The main objective of this paper is to propose an enhanced energy controller for wireless sensor network to optimize and balance power consumption. Multiple studies attempted to achieve power consumption efficiency.

The proposed solution in this network is to minimize the power consumed for transmission and control of communication modes. The sensor is kept in stand-by mode at a certain energy level in which the sensor will always be ready to send and receive messages. Therefore, the energy needed to wake the sensor to be in active state is optimized. In addition, it adds benefit since it decreases delay time and avoids data loss while the sensor is in idle or off state.

The proposed model is powered by two batteries. The main battery B1 is usually a rechargeable AA battery, whereas the second battery B2 is an alternative, and B2 depends on energy harvesting techniques based on the type of environment. In the simulation assumption solar energy harvesting plays a main role as a renewal energy source. B2 is operated when B1 reached the predetermined threshold. In order to maintain balance in power consumption and avoid high fluctuation during switching in communication process and Fig.4. demonstrates how the controller can reduce the fluctuation as mentioned. B2 will continue working until B1 is recharged and then sensor switch back to B1 again as illustrated Fig.5. **Error! Reference source not found.** The power gainer controller manages the swapping policy between the main battery B1 and secondary battery B2. It monitors the energy level consumed and gets the residual energy from the power consumption module in 802.15.4 sensor node.

Fig.4 hysteresis control.

Fig.5 The Proposed system.

The proposed solution follows the hysteresis theory, and it represents the lag between making a change, such as increasing or decreasing power, and the response or effect of that change as illustrated in Fig.6. It typically refers to turn-on and turn-off.

The main aim is to keep the loop curve smoother (less slop) over time to avoid abrupt changes in consumption. Applying the hysteresis loop to the current scenario shows the upward curve (representing the charging process) and the downward curve (representing the consumption). This loop shows the on and off changes.

As shown, point (a) is the threshold of the battery in which the controller can switch to the main battery and continue charging through the harvesting sources. Point (e) is the warning level at 50% of the battery that the controller starts to check the energy level of alternative battery if it is above 50% point (b), the controller can switch to B2. Otherwise, B2 will be allowed to recharge until it reaches the 50% and B1 continue consume up to the minimum threshold point(a), thus the controller will switch to an alternative battery once it reaches 50% and before B1 reaches the threshold level. This permits the controller to have time to check and announce to the central agent if there is no enough power that it needs to find and synchronize the power harvesting storage.

Fig.6 hysteresis loop.

Fig. 7 Battery selection in startup

The primary role of the sensor is to gather information through monitoring and sensing the surrounding environment, then send it to the gateway or process it internally and take action based on the triggered event. In general, the power consumption of the sensor can be summarized as follows [7]:

- 1) Radio transmission and reception are considered the highest consumption of the power source.
- 2) Collisions occur when more than one node needs to be transmitted when the medium is already busy. [8]
- 3) Overhearing occurs when the sensor node keeps receiving data that has already been addressed to another node.
- 4) Control packet overhead for transmission that adds more power consumption by limiting the number of control packets while maintaining reliability which is considered a challenge to meet the quality required for many applications or Realtime apps.
- 5) Idle listening is the waiting status in the node. It keeps the node ready to receive or send data when there is no data to be send or receive which considered wasted power.

The energy consumption in a sensor node is determined by the average rate of the power consumption of the operational time of the node. Accordingly, the sensor operation time includes the communication process of transmitting and receiving signals, sensing, and processing. Furthermore, the sensor can be used in data routing. Each sensor can forward data received from its neighbour directly to the sink node or the closest sensor and then to the sink node. Sensor node uses the highest energy in communication followed by data processing and the least amount of energy is consumed in sensing. By examining the power consumption in the sensor node communication process through Fig.8

Fig.8 sensor power consumption model

P_o refers to the output transmit power while P_{tx} is the transmit power and P_{rx} is the receiver power. P_o and P_{tx} can be considered one term with the highest value of consumption. The differences between transmitting and receiving power in low-power devices are relatively close, nonetheless, the previous power consumption equation model is abstracted as it indicates the basic variables of power consumption through sensor transceiver in the communication process. Therefore, researchers study more comprehensive models attempting to find the optimum solution.

The detailed power consumption cycle model of the sensor leads to finding that switching between different modes SLEEP, TRANSMITTER and RECEIVER can save some power consumption. Nevertheless, fluctuation between active and sleep mode consumes power due to the start-up time every time the node switch between active and sleep mode, which increases the wasted energy consumption.

This is represented in equation (2) and Fig.9. Where N_T is a number of transmissions, P_{te} is the power of transmission per time, T_{on} is time spent in sending, while T_{st} time of steady state. Similarly, for receiving, N_R a number of received packets, R_{on} time while revering and R_{st} is steady state. P_0 is the power consumed at start-up and added to the transmission terms.

$$P_c = N_T[P_{te}(T_{on} + T_{st}) + P_0(T_{on})] + N_R[P_{re}(R_{on} + R_{st})] \quad (2)$$

Fig.9 Transmission sensor power consumption

Many approaches and techniques are proposed to come up with a solution to reduce power consumption, as well as to extend battery lifetime of the sensor.

Fig.10 below shows the classification of all trials that contributed to achieve this reduction.

Fig.10 ISO model classification of energy saving techniques

IV. SIMULATION SETUP

This section aims to monitor and discuss measurements in terms of power consumption while simultaneously using different protocols and technologies. Moreover, this section examines proposed changes to enhance the measurements while using IEEE802.11 and IEEE802.15.4 since the different protocols come within low-power networks.

The current environment simulates different networks of 90m * 90 m. The first network is based on IEEE802.15.4 using narrowband, contains 20 sensors and 2 controllers randomly distributed over the area.

TABLE II - 802.11 NETWORK SETUP

SIMULATION SCENARIO	
Simulation Time	1800sec
X, Y Dimensions	90m * 90 m
Mobility Model	Mass Mobility
Packet size	512 kb
Initial energy	0.5 J
Number of nodes	20 SENSORS
Routing protocol	DYMO ,AODV

TABLE III - 802.15.4 NETWORK SETUP

SIMULATION SCENARIO	
Simulation time	1800 sec

X, Y Dimensions	90m * 90 m
Mobility model	Mass Mobility
MTU	127 Bytes
Initial energy	0.5 J
Number of nodes	20 SENSORS
Routing protocol	DYMO, AODV

Wi-Fi AdHoc network is the second network to adopt the IEEE802.11 standard. It supports IPv4 and ipv6 network protocol. This setup is considered part of the wide grid network, where there is a central station or master agent that collects data from all nodes, monitor and control. Every sensor agent is attached to a harvester that is responsible for regenerating energy for sensor power and energy controller, in addition to being responsible for power source switching.

The master agent can help rerouting data in case the node fails. Each node advertises its energy level. Based on the advertised energy level, the master agent can keep balance in the network.

Initially, two scenarios are run to monitor power consumption in the network to be analysed in case of one power source. In addition, two different protocols AODV and DYMO are tested to determine which will consume less power, which is the first attempt to minimize power consumed in all the simulation.

As previously mentioned,, in this method, the sensor is equipped with a single power source represented as a battery. The network contains two controllers representing the sink node. Sensor nodes are subjected to increased energy consumption due to data transmission and mobility.

As a result of the continuous generation of data from the sensor being sent to the controller packets, queuing may occur, consequently the sensor data experiences a delay to reach the sink node. The average end-to-end delay is the total time taken for the data packet initiated by the sensor to be fully received by the sink node.

Unlike traditional networks, 6LoWPAN nodes are commonly battery-powered, and they always work in tough circumstances for a long time. Therefore, the issue of energy consumption is one of the highest priorities of 6LoWPAN. The issue of optimizing power consumption is discussed by considering 3 main aspects: power consumption, power supply and power management [9][10].

Energy consumption model is always one of interests in studying MAC protocols such as IEEE 802.15.4 devised for energy constrained wireless applications. In the proposed model, to measure the energy consumed in the radio, MAC

module in OMNET++ is allowed to keep tracking all radio states in the PHY module passing through a message passing module. Consequently, the results only show all the counts of changes in the radio state as well as durations. As long as the power for each state is identified in the radio consumption module in OMNET++, the total energy consumption can be easily computed in the proposed model. Different states are used here as an attempt to cover most of the possible working state in a real radio, idle, listening and receiving. It is sensible to find that difference between a transmitting state as receiving is not very far compared to the sleep state.

As previously explained in equation (2), the sensor switching process consumes a lot of the total battery due to the fluctuation between active and sleep mode. The switching process consumes more power to start the sensor from scratch to reach the active mode every time the sensor wakes up. All of the above are illustrated and represented in Fig.11 and Fig.12.[11].

Fig.11 power consumption cycle

Fig.12 Power wasted during waking up

V. RESULTS

System performance is measured by Vectors that record data values as a function of time.

Different scenarios are taken into consideration to figure out the best results through experiments.

Fig.13 Average power consumption in AODV and DYMO IEEE802.15.4

Fig.14 Average power consumption in IEEE802.11

Fig.15 Average end-to-end delay in IEEE802.15.4

Fig.16 Average end-to-end delay in IEEE802.11

The outcome of running the simulation is presented according to the setup in TABLE II and TABLE III. The outcome data from simulation is displayed in Fig.13, Fig.14, Fig.15 and Fig.16 indicate that the DYMO protocol provides a steady performance for the running network with fast performance in finding the route for the data through the dynamic environment changes and ends with less end-to-end delay time. Furthermore, it provides better performance as an On-Demand protocol with less energy

consumption. The network results may present further improvement in terms of considering various propagation models, pause times, mobility models over the routing protocol [12].

Close examination of Fig.17 and Fig.18 shows power consumption of the sensor from waking up to communication state. The highest value went to the start-up process. It took 0.6 seconds to go up, going from 0 watts to 0.0065 watts which is the highest value of the power consumed in the sensor records. With this process repeated, each time the sensor switches from sleep or off mode to the active mode aiming to transmit or receive data, besides additional power will be consumed that can be saved by applying the proposed solution to minimize fluctuating intervals [13].

Fig.17 start-up power consumption

Fig.19 Average power consumption in scenario 1

Table IV- Average power consumption in scenario 1

Battery Level	100%	90%	80%	70%	60%
Average power consumption	0.009	0.0077	0.0057	0.0054	0.0052

Fig.18 Start-up power consumption in the proposed model

The second method is to find out the threshold range of the secondary battery to maintain optimum consumption. Therefore, B1 will start at 60% of its original value as a minimum threshold that is already determined from the previous method. B2 starts with 50% of the B1 value. The sensor will adopt B2 first and B1 will use the alternative renewal power source to recharge. In conjunction with that, the simulator records the value as B2 going down. Starting from 50% to 20% of B2 values, the records are very close which means less fluctuated and less wasted power. Noting that at the level of 70% of B1 which is in the range of power optimization, power consumption is constant through the different levels of B2 from 50% at the start to 20% which is the lowest level of B2 value.

Table V- B1 started with 60%

Battery Level	20%	30%	40%	50%
Average power consumption	0.0052	0.0054	0.0054	0.0054

As stated in the proposed enhanced model, two batteries are attached to the sensor, B1 being the main and B2 being the alternative.

The first scenario is to determine the threshold of the main

Battery B1 starts fully powered and B2 starts with 20% of B1 value. By running the simulation and observing the change in values of B1, it was found that from 80% to 60% the consumption is optimized and inconstancy state.

The first run shows that the system can depend on B2 with a 20% of B1 value, while B1 values can range from 80% to 60%.

Fig. 20 - B2 started with 60%

Table VI- B2 started at 70%

Battery Level	20%	30%	40%	50%
Average power consumption	0.0054	0.0054	0.0054	0.0054

Fig. 21 - B2 started with 70%

Table VII B1 Started with 80%

Battery Level	20%	30%	40%	50%
Average power consumption	0.0057	0.0055	0.0055	0.0055

Fig. 22 - B2 started with 80%

Table VIII - B2 started with 90%

Battery Level	20%	30%	40%	50%
Average power consumption	0.0077	0.0075	0.0075	0.0075

Fig. 23 - B2 started with 90%

By comparing the fluctuation between methods, 90% value was found outside the recommended range and the recommended 70% in our solution that the fluctuation values vary between 5% up and down around the steady state power consumption.

Fig.24 - power consumption at the recommended threshold.

From the graphs shown in the results section, power consumption used in the first method when main battery is full. When the alternative battery is 20%, it indicates that the best optimization for power consumption occurs in the range 80% to 60%. The sensor can consume from B1 until the minimum threshold. The energy levels of both batteries cannot fall below 20% as the lowest level. Less fluctuation and variation in Fig.24 represent increased consumption and more power saving that on the battery.

VI. CONCLUSION

Two batteries are attached to the sensor with the energy manager controller to supervise and control the battery affecting its lifetime as well as consumption. It determines which battery works or needs to work simultaneously with the other battery during harvesting. Setting an energy consumption threshold reduces fluctuations by minimizing the wasted power during the wakeup process by considering Standby mode in active modes. The simulation results showed enhancement in the average network consumption starting from 34% up to 60%. Based on the Experiment, this

enhancement extended battery lifetime, besides the lower fluctuation, not only saves wasted power, but also minimizes start-up time to get the node into transceiver mode to be able to send or receive. Consequently, the sensor node became more reliable and the Quality of Service (QoS) of the network has improved. After the experiment, it is recommended to use two power sources with harvesting techniques and maintaining battery between levels of 60% to 80%. However, future harvesting techniques must be considered, as well as the energy synchronization process between nodes. We believe that enhancing sensor battery recharge time and handling energy requests coming from the sensor energy controller to local storage of the network should increase stability and reliability of the network.

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Improved Discriminatory Ability using Hybrid Feature Selection via Approach Inspired by Grey Wolf Search and Ensemble Classifier for Medical Datasets

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Abstract- Medical datasets inevitably suffer from redundant and irrelevant attributes, which reduce data mining algorithms' ability and often lead to uninterpretable results. Therefore, the first step in medical diagnosis problems is to reduce dimensionality. This paper presents a computational method that takes advantage of wrapper subset evaluation with a meta-heuristic algorithm in a two-phase process to improve the classification performance with a group of meta-classifiers. The first phase filters the feature domain using the information gain ratio in an attribute evaluation method. The first layer's output serves as an input feature for the second phase, which uses grey wolf optimization to find the optimal feature space. An ensemble-based classifier scheme was built based on C4.5, RandF, and ForestPA classifiers to obtain the final decision. The proposed method was validated on several medical datasets of the UCI Machine Learning Repository. The results show that the suggested approach yields significant performance improvements in Accuracy performance compared to other classifiers.

Keywords- Data Mining; Feature Selection; Grey Wolf Optimization; Information Gain Ratio; Ensemble Classifier.

1. INTRODUCTION

Applying pattern recognition algorithms for data mining allows for acquiring important information from large-scale datasets [1]. These techniques are extensively used to discover relationships and functional patterns in data. Data mining techniques are successfully applied in many economic, industrial, scientific, and medical fields to handle massive datasets [2]. Therefore, data reduction techniques are mostly required for filtering, ranking priorities, and providing means to detect and isolate redundant features. These algorithms increase the quality of analyses and the success of recognition systems [3].

Medical Data Mining (MDM) involves using algorithms and techniques to automate disease diagnosis and prediction [4]. Numerous algorithms have been suggested in the medical diagnosis literature and investigated on several benchmark datasets for cancer, heart disorders, and diabetes. The University of Irvine (UCI) has created a public repository of machine learning databases for this purpose [5].

This study's main objective is to provide an entirely automatic decision-support model to help physicians diagnose diseases by finding the most informative features and maximizing classification accuracy. The proposed approach includes two phases before applying a model learning algorithm, which is expected to enhance the algorithm's exploitation capability. The first phase aims to reduce the number of selected features while keeping high classification accuracy. The second phase adds more informative features to increase classification accuracy. Filter methods are known to give high-quality solutions and are computationally inexpensive and efficient, so we used one of the most popular filter methods: information gain (IG) ratio attribute evaluation in the first phase.

Meta-Heuristics algorithms have recently made significant progress in optimization as they eliminate the drawbacks of conventional search techniques, requiring a high complexity cost [6]. This motivates us to apply the grey wolf optimizer (GWO) algorithm in the second feature selection phase. The GWO algorithm is competitive with other meta-heuristic algorithms such as particle swarm optimization (PSO) and has shown resounding

success in many applications [7]. To increase medical datasets' classification ability, we propose an ensemble-based approach that combines C4.5, RandF, and ForestPA algorithms and relies on a voting mechanism for predicting the classification outcome. Experimental results show that the proposed method seems very promising to be applied for diagnosing disease in the early stages.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Sections 2 and 3 describe the dataset that we have worked on and a review of the literature. Section 4 contains the proposed methodology, followed by experiments and a discussion of the results in sections 5 and 6. Finally, section 6 presents the conclusion.

2. MEDICAL DATASETS

The proposed approach has been tested to predict standard publicly available datasets on diseases that mostly influence the quality of life: the heart-statlog, EEG Eye state, diabetic, hepatitis, lung cancer, and Wisconsin Breast Cancer datasets. The datasets were obtained from the UCI Machine Learning Database Repository [5,8,9]. The details of these datasets are shown in Table 1.

Diabetic Retinopathy Dataset

An experiment was carried out on the Diabetic Retinopathy Debrecen dataset based on extracted features from the Messidor image dataset. The dataset used in this study has 1151 instances, 19 features, and two classes.

EEG Eye State Dataset

Rösler and Suendermann provided the EEG eye state dataset from Baden-Wuerttemberg Cooperative State University, Germany. Electrical waves were recorded from electroencephalogram (EEG) signals for 117 seconds to predict the eyes' state as either open or closed. This dataset includes 14,980 instances and 14 features.

Hepatitis Dataset

The dataset was gathered by the Jozef Stefan Institute, Yugoslavia in 1988 during a study to predict the presence or absence of hepatitis based on several medical test results. This database includes 19 features and 154 instances from two classes (“die” and “live”).

Lung Cancer Dataset

Hong and Young provided the lung cancer dataset in 2006 for predicting lung disease from the results of various medical tests. This dataset includes 31 instances and 56 features from two classes.

Heart-Statlog Dataset

This dataset was donated by The Cleveland Clinic Foundation for heart disease prediction. It contains 269 instances taken from patients and healthy people. This dataset has 13 features and two classes, either '1' or '2', based on the absence and presence of Heart disease, respectively.

Wisconsin Breast Cancer Dataset

The Wisconsin Breast Cancer dataset was collected by Dr. William H. Wolberg from 1989 to 1991 at the University of Wisconsin-Madison Hospitals based on fine-needle aspiration biopsy. The dataset contains 698 instances and nine features.

Table 1
DESCRIPTION OF SELECTED DATASETS

Dataset	Number of features	Number of instances	Imbalance ratio
1. Diabetes	19	1151	1.13
2. Human's cognition state	14	14980	1.22

3. Hepatitis disease	19	154	3.84
4. Lung Cancer	56	31	1.44
5. Heart disease	13	269	1.25
6. Breast Cancer	9	698	1.89

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Recently, researchers have begun to consider applying feature selection methods in classification problems. A hybrid machine learning model was proposed by Kaya and Uyar [10] to identify hepatitis based on a rough set and an extreme learning machine. They used a hepatitis dataset from the UCI repository to test their hybrid model. They produced 20 reducts with a range of 3-7 attributes using rough set theory. The reducts were selected first, and then the records with missing values were removed from each one. The classification accuracy obtained using an extreme learning machine was 100% with the reduct of four attributes when using 80% of the training data. The obtained reduct set had only 87 records.

Sartakhti et al. [11] developed a hybrid system using a support vector machine (SVM) and simulated annealing for detecting hepatitis. By removing the missing values, the researchers reduced the size of the dataset to 80 samples. The suggested method was tested with a 10-fold cross-validation procedure, and parameters were tuned for enhancing the classification accuracy. They achieved an accuracy of 96.25%.

A prediction technique for heart disease risk was developed using weighted fuzzy rules [12]. The technique was tested on data from Cleveland, Hungary, and Switzerland. The technique started with removing missing values and grouping instances based on the class label. After discretization, the weighted fuzzy rule was applied to a Mamdani fuzzy inference system. The obtained classification accuracy of 0.51–0.62, 0.71–0.47, and 0.36–0.51 for the Cleveland, Hungarian, and Switzerland datasets. An automatic rough set-based SVM classifier and tested using the Wisconsin Breast Cancer dataset [13]. After fine-tuning the SVM parameters, they achieved an accuracy of 100% with five attributes. Vijaya et al. [14] proposed a fuzzy-neurogenetic-based model to predict cardiovascular disease severity and tested it with the Cleveland Heart Disease dataset. They used a trapezoidal membership function for the fuzzification process to train the neural to identify the most significant fuzzy rules. A sigmoidal activation function was applied for both the hidden layer and output layer neurons. They also applied a genetic algorithm to tune the weight associated between nodes. The reported classification accuracy of the system was 88.35%.

Sahan et al. [15] developed a hybrid machine learning method for a fuzzy-artificial immune system with a k-nearest-neighbor algorithm for diagnosis using the Wisconsin Breast Cancer dataset. The classification accuracy of the suggested system was 99.4%. Chen et al. [16] proposed an analytical approach by integrating PSO and the 1-NN method to address a liver disorder dataset's feature selection. The correct classification rate of the proposed system with 5-fold cross-validation was 68.99%. Pashaei et al. [17] improved the performance of PSO combined with a C4.5 decision tree by integrating a boosted C5.0 decision tree as a fitness function. The experimental results over five medical datasets from the UCI repository showed that the proposed method improved the performance of PSO and C4.5 and obtained a higher accuracy rate.

Vijayashree and Sultana [18] investigated applying PSO with SVM to proposed a heart disease classification method and reported a classification accuracy of 84.36%. Li et al. [19] suggested a nonlinear transformation technique based on a fuzzy method to find classification information in original data attribute values for a small dataset. They used an SVM as a classifier. The correct classification rate of the proposed system was 70.85% for

the Liver Disorder dataset. Antal and Hajdu [20] proposed an ensemble-based method for identifying the presence of diabetic retinopathy disease. The proposed system's obtained classification results showed 90% sensitivity, 91% specificity, 90% accuracy, and an AUC of 0.989. Naseriparsa and Kashani [21] applied a Naïve Bayes classifier two-stage classification model for enhancing the classification of lung cancer. The suggested model starts with applying PCA to eliminate irrelevant features. Next, Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) resampling technique is considered to handle the imbalanced class distribution.

We have observed that several machine learning models applied several feature selection algorithms to enhance the classification performance for disease diagnostic. We propose a novel method that combines feature selection benefits and an ensemble classifier for enhancing medical data discrimination and detection accuracy. The next section provides more detail on the proposed model techniques.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Feature selection is the process of selecting distinctive features by excluding irrelevant and redundant ones. The reduction of features aims to find the essential feature set. This eventually reduces the processing time and enhances the classification accuracy, particularly in MDM [3]. Medical datasets indeed contain plenty of such attributes, which lower data mining algorithms' efficacy [22]. To increase medical datasets' classification ability, we propose a hybrid filter-metaheuristic optimization-based feature selection approach with a voting mechanism's ensemble of classifiers.

The proposed approach combines IG with GWO to enhance the feature selection process's efficiency and overall accuracy. Consequently, using a reduced number of features would cause the search process to converge faster and make it less expensive. In the first stage, we select features through the IG technique, and in the second stage, we apply the GWO technique to construct a new conceptual vector space based on the reductive feature vector space and discover the important associative relationships between features. Then, we build an ensemble-based model that combines C4.5, RandF, and ForestPA, which relies on a voting mechanism for the final classification decision making.

4.1 Information Gain Ratio (IG) Attribute Evaluation

The IG measure is based on the Shannon entropy to select a test attribute at each node within the C4.5 decision tree algorithm [23]. It measures how precisely the attributes predict a test dataset's classes; then, it assigns the "best" attribute as the decision tree's root. The estimated IG needed to classify a given sample s from a set of data samples C , $IG(s,C)$, is calculated as follows.

$$IG(s, C) = \frac{gain(s,C)}{split_info(C)}, \tag{1}$$

$$gain(s, C) = entropy(s, C) - entropy_p(s, C),$$

$$entropy(s, C) = -p(s|C) \log_2 p(s|C) - (1 - p(s|C)) \log_2 (1 - p(s|C)),$$

$$p(s, C) = freq(s|C) / |C|,$$

$$entropy_p(s, C) = \sum_i \frac{|C_i|}{|C|} entropy_p(s, C_i),$$

$$split_info(C) = -\sum_i \frac{|C_i|}{|C|} \log \frac{|C_i|}{|C|},$$

where $freq(s,C)$, C_i and $|C_i|$ represent the frequency of the sample s in C , the i^{th} class of C and the number of samples in C_i , respectively.

4.2 Grey Wolf Optimization Algorithm

The GWO algorithm is a population-based metaheuristic algorithm that was introduced by Mirjalili in 2014 [24]. The GWO algorithm is primarily motivated by the leadership and hunting behaviors of grey wolves in nature, which most prefer to live in a pack. Each pack's average size varies from 5 to 12 wolves with a strict hierarchy, and each wolf in the group has a defined role in the hunting process [25]. Each herd has four foremost ranks that are modeled as a pyramid [24].

The first level in the hierarchy of grey wolves is the pack leader called alpha (α). This level is responsible for decisions about all wolf behaviors. Beta (β) wolves are the second level and are responsible for helping in some decisions for the other wolves in the packs. The third level is the delta (δ) wolves and are responsible for watching the territory's boundaries, protecting the group, hunting, etc. The last level in the hierarchal model is called omega (ω), which is the weakest of the wolves, as it should obey other individuals' orders [26].

The second inspiration of GWO is that wolves are known for their group-hunting strategy to catch prey. The hunting process starts with tracking and chasing the prey, then encircling and harassing until it finally stops moving before attacking. According to the GWO algorithm, the alpha, beta, and delta represent the first, second, third-best solutions. The remaining candidate solutions are regarded as omegas. The wolves can encircle their prey during the hunting process in a manner that can be mathematically modeled as:

$$\vec{D} = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}_p - \vec{X}(t)| \tag{2}$$

$$\vec{X}(t + 1) = |\vec{X}_p(t) - \vec{A} \cdot \vec{D}|$$

where \vec{X} and \vec{X}_p represent the positions of the prey and grey wolf at an iteration (t), respectively. \vec{A} and \vec{C} are coefficient vectors that can be formulated as follows:

$$\vec{A} = |2a \cdot \overrightarrow{rand_1} - \vec{a}| \tag{3}$$

$$\vec{C} = 2 \cdot \overrightarrow{rand_2}$$

where $\overrightarrow{rand_1}$ and $\overrightarrow{rand_2}$ are random vectors in [0,1]. \vec{a} is linearly decreasing from 2 to zero over iterations as follows:

$$a = 2 - t * \frac{2}{iterations} \tag{4}$$

The parameter iterations determine the maximum number of iterations. The grey wolf position (X,Y) can be updated according to the position of the prey (X*,Y*). The best grey wolf position can be updated by adjusting the vectors \vec{A} and \vec{C} . To mimic the hunting behavior, the alpha, beta, and delta are aware of the potential locations of the prey. As the alpha, beta, and delta indicate the best three solutions, the rest of the wolves update their positions according to the best three solutions (\vec{X}_1, \vec{X}_2 , and \vec{X}_3). This can be expressed as follows:

$$\vec{X}(t + 1) = (\vec{X}_1 + \vec{X}_2 + \vec{X}_3) / 3 \tag{5}$$

$$\vec{X}_1 = \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{A}_1 \cdot (\vec{D}_\alpha), \vec{D}_\alpha = |\vec{C} \cdot \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{X}|$$

$$\vec{X}_2 = \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{A}_2 \cdot (\vec{D}_\beta) \cdot \vec{D}_\beta = |\vec{C}_2 \cdot \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{X}| \quad ,$$

$$\vec{X}_3 = \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{A}_3 \cdot (\vec{D}_\delta) \cdot \vec{D}_\delta = |\vec{C}_3 \cdot \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{X}|$$

When attacking the prey, each wolf updates its position between its current position and the prey's position so that $|A| < 1$. In searching for the prey, the alpha, beta, and delta wolves go away from searching for the prey and converge when attacking the prey. A_1 can take random values less than -1 or greater than 1 to force the wolves to diverge from the prey.

4.3 On Ensemble Classifiers

Ensemble learning is a paradigm applied in machine learning where several individual classification base models are trained to solve the same problem. Ensemble methods' primary objective is to achieve more accurate classification rates than a single model usually accomplishes [20]. Ensemble methods try to train multiple learning machines and combine their predictions to obtain better accuracy. This paradigm is decisive in achieving an estimation result with higher stability and accuracy by combining multiple independent classification models [27].

Several algorithms were chosen to build ensemble learning models: bagging, boosting, voting, Bayesian parameter averaging and stacking[28]. Numerous studies have proven that decision trees are very effective methods of supervised learning [29]. Among decision tree algorithms, C4.5 has been widely used in data mining due to its high efficiency in handling continuous, discrete attributes and missing values [18]. Meanwhile, RandF is generally more straightforward and can achieve accurate and robust results than single decision trees [30]. Moreover, ForestPA is a class implementing decision forest algorithm that generates trees with high precision based on the feature space's strength. With its novel weight assignment strategy, bootstrap sampling, and penalized attributes, ForestPA generates highly diverse trees while retaining their higher individual accuracy [31].

4.3.1 C4.5 decision tree Classifier

C4.5 is one of the most widely used decision tree algorithms and is an enhanced version of the ID3 algorithm. Its capabilities in approximating discrete-valued functions robust to noisy data are known for their capabilities, in which the learned function is represented by a decision tree [32]. Moreover, C4.5 can handle missing attribute values, which are very common in medical data [17]. The C4.5 algorithm uses the IG ratio as the default attribute choice criterion to choose the best splitting attributes. This algorithm starts with visiting each node to select an optimal split based on the IG ratio's maximization and assigns it as the root node of a tree. Then, it constructs a leaf intended for all of the probable values. The algorithm's main task is to determine the best proper attribute to partition the data into several classes.

4.3.2. RandomForest (RandF)Classifier

RandF algorithm is a tree-based-ensemble classifier based on a combination tree of predictors where each tree depends on the values of a random vector sampled independently and with the same distribution for all trees [30]. RandF builds a combination of individual base classifiers and accelerates the building speed. Each tree is generated using a random vector sampled independently from the classification input vector. The final classification decision is estimated by collecting the votes from all the trees using a rule-based approach (such as majority voting, product, sum, or Bayesian rules) or based on an iterative error minimization technique through reducing the weights for the correctly classified samples.

4.3.3. Forest by Penalizing Attributes (ForestPA) Classifier

Unlike other algorithms that use a subset of the non-class attributes, ForestPA builds a set of highly accurate decision trees by exploiting the strength of all non-class attributes available in a dataset [31]. Simultaneously, some weight-related concerns, such as the weight assignment strategy and weight increment strategy, are considered to retain individual accuracy and promote substantial diversity. ForestPA is constructed by penalizing attributes that are used in previous trees in a decision forest. An attribute tested at a lower level can influence more logic rules than an attribute tested at a higher level, so ForestPA imposes weights in a systematic way such that an attribute that is tested at a lower level receives a lower weight/higher penalty than an attribute tested at a higher level. Additionally, ForestPA randomly selects the weight of an attribute from the weight range allocated for the attribute's level.

4.3.4. Voting Mechanism

Voting is one of the most common intuitive ensemble combination techniques and performs decision-making based on combining several classifiers' outcomes. The decision-making applies a combination rule using the power of several individual classifiers [20,28,32], such as the minimum, maximum, majority, product, and average of probabilities. To obtain the final result in this study, every prediction is subjected to voting to decide the final prediction decision. Consider C target classes testing instance x_t . Each base classifier (h_j) provides a prediction Y_j for testing instance x_t for the target class.

a. Majority Voting rule

According to the majority rule, all classifiers will vote on the class to predict the data, and the class with the most votes will be selected. Majority voting aims to produce a combined prediction for input x , and a binary function can be used to represent the votes:

$$x_t \rightarrow Y_i \text{ satisfy } \max \sum_{i=1}^L \Delta_i(Y_i|x_t) \tag{6}$$

$$\text{Where } \Delta_i(Y_i|x_t) = \begin{cases} 1; & \text{if } h_j(x_t) = Y_i \\ 0; & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Later, the votes from all C_i 's classifiers are summed, and the label with the highest vote will be the predicted class. In this case, base classifiers' number and performance play a great role in the ensemble classifier's accuracy [33]. Combining the decisions with majority vote criteria has lower computational complexity and requires much less time overhead.

b. Average of Probabilities

In this technique, classifiers vote on all classes with a vote equal to each class's classification accuracy. For example, if two classifiers classify a problem with 80% and 60% accuracy, then during the voting process, this will assign the two classes to 0.8 and 0.6 votes, respectively. The final decision will be the class with the most significant number of votes. The Arithmetic Average rule is defined as discovering the maximal value of P_j 's arithmetic average ($Y_j|x_t$) as specified in Eq. 7.

$$x_t \rightarrow Y_i \text{ satisfy } \max_{Y_i} \frac{1}{L} \sum_{j=1}^L P_j(Y_i|x_t) \tag{7}$$

c. Maximum voting rule

In the minimum or maximum voting rule, probabilities of all classifier's predictions are combined, and a class is assigned based on this value. The maximum rule selects the predicted class label depending on the information provided by P_j 's maximal value ($Y_i|x_t$) across all potential class labels, as specified in Eq. 8.

$$x_t \rightarrow Y_i \text{ satisfy } \max_{v_i} \{ \max_j (P_j(Y_i|x_t)) \} \tag{8}$$

5. EXPERIMENTAL WORK AND DISCUSSION

Training and evaluation of models were performed using 10-fold cross-validation, in which nine folds of data are used to train the classifier, and one-fold is used for testing the classifier. This is performed ten times, and accordingly, testing and training encompass all ten folds to prevent a model from being overfitted to the dataset. When learning medical data, measures such as accuracy and the error rate usually favor the majority class [34,35]. To evaluate our approach's feasibility in the medical domain, we applied the 10-fold cross-validation procedure through all the experiments. The selected classifiers' accuracy was calculated using the sensitivity, specificity, balanced accuracy, precision, and *f*-measure, which are more appropriate for imbalanced datasets [36]. The main formulations are defined in Equations 6-10 according to the confusion matrix of a two-class problem.

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \tag{6}$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \tag{7}$$

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{TP}{TP+NP} + \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \right) \tag{8}$$

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \tag{9}$$

$$f\text{-measure} = \frac{2 \times TP}{2 \times TP + FP + FN} \tag{10}$$

To determine which of the three techniques is the most suitable for the classification problem (C4.5, RandF, or ForestPA classifiers), we start performing classification over the entire dataset. We compared the performance of the suggested ensemble learning model with that of the three classifiers. Results obtained from Table 2 suggest that the ensemble algorithm has the highest values with the diabetic and Lung Cancer datasets, whereas RandF outperformed the other algorithms in the EEG Eye state and statlog heart datasets. However, all classifiers had comparable performance in most cases. Overall, when all features are considered for classification, the balanced accuracy is above 80%.

In the first step, the essential features are identified using the IG-based feature selection method to evaluate the reduced feature subset's reliability. Tables 3 and 4 show the numbers and names of selected features and their classification results from the medical datasets. By implementing IG alone, the approach reduced the dimensionality drastically and eliminated the dataset's irrelevant features by between 14% and 80%. The selection of relevant features by the IG algorithm has significantly enhanced the overall classification performance in most datasets. After the application of IG, the average of balanced accuracy is above 90%. The results show that the

majority-based voting mechanism performs better than the other voting mechanisms in most cases. At this stage, the suggested ensemble algorithm and the other classifiers had comparable performance.

In the second step, to significantly improve the predictive performance, we reduced the first phase using the GWO technique. Then, the remaining features were fed into the meta-classifiers. The pre-step feature selection and comparison of the datasets are shown in Table 5 and Table 6. Adding the GWO algorithm considerably reduces dimensionality and eliminates the datasets' irrelevant features by between 46% and 93%. Notably, the proposed feature selection approach outperforms all other features in every aspect, and the IG-GWO-ensemble approach achieves the highest accuracy rate.

For instance, in the lung cancer dataset, the IG-GWO-ensemble approach outperforms all other individual classifiers and achieves the highest balanced accuracy rates of 91.5%, 90.5%, and 90.5% subsets of 56, 11, and 4 features, respectively. Moreover, the suggested technique helped improve the accuracy rate of the hepatitis dataset by 87.2%, 89.6%, and 88.5% with subsets of 19, 6, and 3 features, respectively. Additionally, classification methods using the three base classifiers obtained excellent results when applied to datasets with imbalanced data distribution. There were no significant performance differences during the second phase regarding the EEG eye state since the features were dramatically reduced.

The IG-GWO-ensemble approach was frequently found to be among the well-performing methods. In many cases, this classifier could handle imbalance very well. IG-GWO-ensemble was consistently the best performing classifier in most datasets. Both RandF and ForestPA tended to yield higher sensitivity, specificity, and precision values, while C4.5 bagging provided better results in terms of the *f*-measure. The performance of the classifiers on different datasets remained almost the same. Overall, the best classifiers performed well regardless of the type of data or the degree of class imbalance.

Table 2
FULL DATASET-COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE UNPROCESSED DATASET (WITH ALL THE ORIGINAL FEATURES)

Dataset	Classifier		Sensitivity	Specificity	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	<i>f</i> -measure
Diabetic	Ensemble	Maj	0.642	0.704	0.851	0.710	0.674
		Max	0.650	0.687	0.843	0.667	0.701
		Avg	0.653	0.704	0.851	0.677	0.714
	C4.5		0.612	0.680	0.839	0.684	0.646
	RandF		0.637	0.594	0.796	0.640	0.638
	ForestPA		0.653	0.654	0.826	0.681	0.667
EEG Eye State	Ensemble	Maj	0.895	0.948	0.974	0.933	0.914
		Max	0.833	0.870	0.935	0.854	0.839
		Avg	0.864	0.912	0.956	0.890	0.888
	C4.5		0.825	0.861	0.931	0.829	0.827
	RandF		0.907	0.960	0.980	0.949	0.927
	ForestPA		0.867	0.924	0.962	0.903	0.885
Hepatitis	Ensemble	Maj	0.543	0.762	0.872	0.655	0.594
		Max	0.571	0.702	0.843	0.643	0.615
		Avg	0.529	0.714	0.849	0.630	0.607
	C4.5		0.571	0.714	0.849	0.625	0.597
	RandF		0.457	0.798	0.889	0.653	0.538
	ForestPA		0.571	0.762	0.873	0.667	0.615
Lung Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.444	1.000	0.915	1.000	0.615
		Max	0.556	0.909	0.883	0.806	0.714
		Avg	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.839	0.833
	C4.5		0.556	0.909	0.883	0.714	0.625
	RandF		0.333	0.955	0.874	0.750	0.462
	ForestPA		0.333	1.000	0.896	1.000	0.500
Statlog Heart	Ensemble	Maj	0.782	0.867	0.929	0.823	0.802
		Max	0.756	0.833	0.912	0.799	0.783
		Avg	0.773	0.840	0.916	0.810	0.793
	C4.5		0.748	0.820	0.906	0.767	0.757
	RandF		0.773	0.880	0.936	0.836	0.803
	ForestPA		0.765	0.853	0.922	0.805	0.784

Wisconsin Breast Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.959	0.967	0.981	0.939	0.949
		Max	0.934	0.961	0.978	0.951	0.926
		Avg	0.938	0.965	0.980	0.956	0.934
	C4.5		0.934	0.961	0.978	0.926	0.930
	RandF		0.967	0.972	0.984	0.947	0.957
	ForestPA		0.971	0.965	0.980	0.936	0.953

Table 3
SELECTED FEATURES BASED ON IG IN THE FIRST STEP

Dataset	No. Of attributes	Selected attributes	Reduction %
Diabetic	13	3,15,16,4,14,5,9,6,13,7,8,2,1	-30%
EEG Eye State	12	7,6,1,14,13,12,9,10,11,5,8,4	-14%
Hepatitis	6	14,13,12,1,18,5	-68%
Statlog Heart	10	13,3,12,9,8,10,11,2,1,7	-23%
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	8	2,3,6,7,5,8,1,4	-11%

Table 4
PERFORMANCE CLASSIFICATION FOR FEATURE SELECTION BASED ON IG IN THE FIRST STEP

Dataset	Classifier		Sensitivity	Specificity	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	f-measure
Diabetic	Ensemble	Maj	0.656	0.713	0.856	0.721	0.687
		Max	0.628	0.694	0.846	0.659	0.699
		Avg	0.637	0.712	0.855	0.672	0.715
	C4.5		0.574	0.719	0.858	0.698	0.630
	RandF		0.669	0.713	0.856	0.725	0.696
	ForestPA		0.681	0.643	0.821	0.683	0.682
EEG Eye State	Ensemble	Maj	0.881	0.934	0.967	0.916	0.898
		Max	0.818	0.865	0.932	0.844	0.831
		Avg	0.853	0.898	0.949	0.878	0.872
	C4.5		0.808	0.848	0.924	0.812	0.810
	RandF		0.890	0.949	0.974	0.934	0.912
	ForestPA		0.851	0.910	0.955	0.885	0.868
Hepatitis	Ensemble	Maj	0.500	0.810	0.896	0.686	0.579
		Max	0.486	0.798	0.889	0.656	0.667
		Avg	0.486	0.798	0.889	0.656	0.667
	C4.5		0.443	0.833	0.907	0.689	0.539
	RandF		0.414	0.738	0.859	0.569	0.479
	ForestPA		0.529	0.762	0.872	0.649	0.583
Lung Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.833	0.667
		Max	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.839	0.833
		Avg	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.839	0.833
	C4.5		0.556	0.909	0.883	0.714	0.625
	RandF		0.556	0.864	0.861	0.625	0.588
	ForestPA		0.444	1.000	0.915	1.000	0.615
Statlog Heart	Ensemble	Maj	0.773	0.880	0.936	0.836	0.803
		Max	0.765	0.847	0.919	0.810	0.798
		Avg	0.765	0.853	0.922	0.814	0.805
	C4.5		0.739	0.840	0.915	0.786	0.762
	RandF		0.782	0.867	0.929	0.823	0.802
	ForestPA		0.782	0.867	0.929	0.823	0.802
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.963	0.967	0.981	0.939	0.951
		Max	0.938	0.961	0.978	0.953	0.926
		Avg	0.938	0.965	0.980	0.956	0.934
	C4.5		0.934	0.961	0.978	0.926	0.930
	RandF		0.967	0.969	0.983	0.943	0.955
	ForestPA		0.963	0.963	0.979	0.932	0.947

Table 5
SELECTED FEATURES BASED ON IG-GWO IN THE SECOND STEP

Dataset	No. Of attributes	IG-GWO	Reduction %
Diabetic	5	1,3,7,13,14	-74%
EEG Eye State	1	12	-93%
Hepatitis	3	1,3,4	-84%
Lung Cancer	4	1,2,3,9	-93%
Statlog Heart	7	3,4,5,7,8,9,10	-46%
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	6	1,2,4,5,6,8	-33%

Table 6
PERFORMANCE CLASSIFICATION FOR FEATURE SELECTION BASED ON IG-GWO IN THE SECOND STEP

Dataset	Classifier		Sensitivity	Specificity	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	f-measure
Diabetic	Ensemble	Maj	0.669	0.674	0.836	0.699	0.684
		Max	0.668	0.687	0.843	0.677	0.707
		Avg	0.664	0.693	0.846	0.678	0.710
	C4.5		0.614	0.696	0.847	0.692	0.650
	RandF		0.674	0.657	0.828	0.690	0.682
	ForestPA		0.678	0.630	0.814	0.674	0.676
EEG Eye State	Ensemble	Maj	0.417	0.761	0.880	0.587	0.488
		Max	0.408	0.764	0.882	0.604	0.584
		Avg	0.415	0.761	0.880	0.605	0.585
	C4.5		0.418	0.760	0.880	0.586	0.488
	RandF		0.368	0.768	0.884	0.563	0.446
	ForestPA		0.420	0.757	0.878	0.585	0.489
Hepatitis	Ensemble	Maj	0.600	0.786	0.885	0.700	0.646
		Max	0.600	0.786	0.885	0.701	0.700
		Avg	0.586	0.786	0.885	0.695	0.695
	C4.5		0.586	0.798	0.890	0.707	0.641
	RandF		0.600	0.786	0.885	0.700	0.646
	ForestPA		0.586	0.786	0.885	0.695	0.636
Lung Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.833	0.667
		Max	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.839	0.833
		Avg	0.556	0.955	0.905	0.839	0.833
	C4.5		0.556	0.909	0.883	0.714	0.625
	RandF		0.556	0.955	0.905	0.833	0.667
	ForestPA		0.444	1.000	0.915	1.000	0.615
Statlog Heart	Ensemble	Maj	0.765	0.900	0.945	0.858	0.809
		Max	0.748	0.887	0.939	0.825	0.840
		Avg	0.739	0.887	0.939	0.822	0.838
	C4.5		0.748	0.887	0.939	0.840	0.791
	RandF		0.739	0.880	0.935	0.830	0.782
	ForestPA		0.798	0.860	0.926	0.819	0.809
Wisconsin Breast Cancer	Ensemble	Maj	0.963	0.963	0.979	0.932	0.947
		Max	0.954	0.958	0.977	0.957	0.924
		Avg	0.959	0.958	0.977	0.958	0.924
	C4.5		0.950	0.959	0.977	0.923	0.937
	RandF		0.963	0.963	0.979	0.932	0.947
	ForestPA		0.967	0.963	0.979	0.932	0.949

Table 7 show that the proposed IG-GWO-ensemble technique performed better than previous studies regarding the EEG eye state, statlog-heart, and lung cancer datasets from the UCI repository. Nevertheless, the classification accuracy on the other datasets was notably enhanced as the number of features was reduced. Tables 3, 5, and 7 show that ensemble values are, for the most part, better than the values of the individual learning models on all five metrics. The results showed an excellent average correctness rate of the studies performed so far on all medical datasets by employing the IG-GWO-ensemble model. Furthermore, due to the subsets' dimensionality reduction, the proposed IG-GWO-ensemble model reduced the time overhead when applied to the feature selection and ensemble model. The results strongly suggest that the proposed IG-GWO-ensemble model could aid in the dimensionality reduction and diagnosis of diseases, and it could be beneficial to physicians for making final decisions about patients.

Table 7
COMPARISON OF IG-GWO-ENSEMBLE AND PREVIOUS RESEARCH RESULTS (ACCURACY IN %)

Author/ Technique	Dataset					
	Diabetic	EEG Eye State	Hepatitis	Lung Cancer	Statlog Heart	Wisconsin Breast Cancer
[11]			96.25%			
[12]					62.0%	
[15]						99.4%
[18]					84.36%	
[37]		96.0%				
[21]	90.0%					

[22]				83.0%		
Full dataset	85.1%	98.0%	88.9%	91.5%	93.6%	98.4%
IG	85.8%	97.4%	90.7%	91.5%	93.6%	98.3%
IG-GWO	84.7%	88.4%	89.0%	90.5%	94.5%	97.9%

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study presented a method designed for use in diagnosis based on several medical datasets. We have developed a two-step feature selection technique to eliminate non-essential features, which enhanced the classification performance. The GWO algorithm was used for the feature selection process and IG ratio attribute evaluation to optimize the efficiency of the feature selection process and enhance the accuracy of the classification with voting criteria. The results showed that the performance of the ensemble method seems very promising for MDM.

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BI-TEMPORAL IMPLEMENTATION IN RELATIONAL DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS: MS SQL SERVER

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Abstract. Traditional database management systems (DBMS) are the computation storage and reservoir of large amounts of information. The data accumulated by these database systems is the information valid at present time, valid now. It is the data that is true at the present moment. Past data is the information that was kept in the database at an earlier time, data that is hold to be existed in the past, were valid at some point before now. Future data is the information supposed to be valid at a future time instance, data that will be true in the near future, valid at some point after now. The commercial DBMS of today used by organizations and individuals, such as MS SQL Server, Oracle, DB2, Sybase, Postgres etc., do not provide models to support and process (retrieving, modifying, inserting and removing) past and future data.

The implementation of bi-temporal modelling in Microsoft SQL Server is important to know how relational database management system handles data the bi-temporal property. In bi-temporal database, data saved is never deleted and additional values are always appended. Therefore, the paper explores one of the way we can build bi-temporal handling of data. The paper aims to build the core concepts of bi-temporal data storage and querying techniques used in bi-temporal relational DBMS i.e., from data structures to normalized storage, and to extraction or slicing of data.

The unlimited growth of data results relational data to become complicated in terms of management and storage of data. Thus, the developers working in various commercial and industrial applications should know how bi-temporal concepts apply

to relational databases, especially due to their increased flexibility in the bi-temporal storage as well as in analyzing data. Thereby, the paper demonstrates how bi-temporal data structures and their operations are applied in Relational Database Management System.

Keywords: Bi-temporal Databases, Databases, Normalization, MS SQL Server Bi-temporal Database.

1 INTRODUCTION

The most data in systems, nowadays are temporal. The trivial task is described as tracking the validity of an entity in a single point in time. But, bi-temporality includes another dimension to the system. Bi-temporal model supports two different timelines - valid time and transaction time. First one is an object's factual time and transaction time denotes when objects are known to the database. The notion is 'what you know' and 'when you knew it'.

Bi-temporality is a solution in database implementation of financial institutions, trading, legal practices or even medicine. When there is an option to return in time to an earlier period of history, some of common complexities become of little worth. For example, in medicine, bi-temporality can present more precise patient history. You can then correlate illnesses with pre-existing conditions. Furthermore law practices can significantly benefit from this. Knowing which laws were active during given time interval, it can be applied to legal artefacts.

Nevertheless, financial institutions can use bi-temporal system to comply with financial regulations - for example, having transparent trading – i.e., uniformed, consistent data and rewinding trading metrics. The first problem that can arise in a traditional system is scalability issue. Conventional database management systems approach involves adding more physical or virtual resources to the underlying server hosting the database – more CPU, more memory or more storage i.e, designed to be vertically scaled. Such architecture creates both technological and business barriers that will not be easy to solve. Second problem is adjusting to modern data structures, which in itself could be a tedious task. Variety of different services and features which not all relational databases are equipped to handle, which are leading to diverse data structures,. In addition to this, there is one more issue, that is equally important - speed.

Data saving or retrieving speed is significant to any database management system. The extension of relational database management system can be an efficient solution to this when considering the scalability and performance metrics such as speed in execution and extraction of data in old database systems.

The paper is organized as, proposed algorithm explained in

section II, model in section III, bi-temporal data definition language are presented in section IV, bi-temporal data manipulation language in section V and Concluding remarks are given in section VI.

2 LITREATURE REVIEW

In the thesis, “A Generalisation Approach to Temporal Data Models and their Implementations” explains about A Temporal Relational DBMS: TimeDB. In this dissertation [2], the author showcases that, a temporal data model has:

1. Valid time and/or transaction time as well as other time lines.
2. Temporal data structures do not make any hypothesis about a specific type system or the presence of specific time attributes.
3. Temporal data structures has time stamping of all constructs supported by the model.
4. Temporal data structures can also overcome the vertical temporal anomaly.
5. A temporally complete query language or algebra which has snapshot reducible semantics.
6. Temporal constraints with snapshot reducible semantics.

The bi-temporal relational DBMS, Time DB agrees the language ATSQL2. It is the result of process of uniting three different approaches, namely

1. ATSQL2, a temporal query language on SQL.
2. Chrono Log, which introduces the concept of temporal completeness.
3. Bi-temporal ChronoSQL, featuring a bi-temporal query language.

The translation algorithm used in Time DB is, a temporal query is converted into a temporal algebra expression using the temporal set operations union ($\cup t$), intersect ($\cap t$) and difference ($\setminus t$). Each argument to set operations is either a simple algebra expression using a temporal select (σt), project (πt) and cross product ($\times t$) operation or the result of another temporal set operation. Each simple algebra expression using only a combination of a select, project and cross product operation can then be evaluated separately using a standard SELECT-FROM-WHERE statement. These intermediate results are stored in temporary tables and then used to calculate other parts of the expression.

In Time DB, a valid-time interval $I = [vts_#\$ - vte_#\$]$, closed at the lower bound and open at the upper, is mapped internally to two attributes $vts_#\$$ (valid-time start) and $vte_#\$$ (valid time end). Thus, each valid-time relation can have two additional (hidden) attributes. Transaction-time tables are extended accordingly. Bitemporal tables contain attributes for both valid time and transaction time. Bi-temporal Algebra Operations Time DB handles bi-temporal queries. For these queries, special operations for set union, set difference, set

intersection and cross product need to be implemented. A bi-temporal query is translated to standard SQL the same way as a unitemporal query. It uses bi-temporal algebra operations instead.

In the paper [22] Modeling and Querying Multidimensional Bitemporal Data Warehouses, by Canan Eren Atay¹, Gözde Alp^{2*} states that a Bitemporal atom is defined as a triplet, where the valid and transaction time components can be deduced as a time point, a time interval, or a temporal element. A Bitemporal atom in the form of represents Valid time lower bound (VT_LB), Valid time upper bound (VT_UB) ,Transaction time lower bound (TT_LB), Transaction time upper bound (TT_UB) and Data value, respectively.

Richard T. Snodgrass, Michael H. Böhlen, Christian S. Jensen, and Andreas Steiner states in their book that many applications need to keep track of the past states of the database, often for auditing requirements. Changes are not permitted on the past states; that would disrupt secure auditing. Instead, compensating transactions are used to correct errors. When an error is encountered, often the analyst will look at the state of the database at a previous point in time to determine where and how the error occurred. The integrity of the previous states of the database is preserved, so the solution is to have the DBMS maintain transaction time automatically.

In the paper [14] Exploiting bitemporal schema versions for managing an historical medical data warehouse: A case study, by Maria-Trinidad SERNA-ENCINAS* Michel ADIBA proposes that for the management, storage and visualization of a data warehouse with current and historical data, in a medical environment, we propose to use bitemporal schema versions adapted to warehouse. Nevertheless, versions management is a complex task and presents several problems. The main problem for us is the versions explosion. Thus, we must establish a mechanism to control this problem. Our proposition considers:

- An operator called SetVersion that allows to apply a set of changes on a version to generate a new version.
- A set of primitives for managing schema versions and cubes, dimensions and hierarchies.
- An evolution manager responsible for different historical schema versions management.
- A set of integrity rules that restraint the primitive execution.

3 PROPOSED MODEL

The main goal presented here, is to create comprehensive SQL bi-temporal database. For achieving the goal, these criteria must be met:

- Build bi-temporal data structure.
- Investigate how to construct normalization for data and referential integrity.
- Analyze bi-temporal manipulation techniques. (insertion, change, deletion)
- Inspect bi-temporal data extraction techniques. (coalescing, slicing)
- Outline assorted bi-temporal data extraction operations and implement them.

The solution is to have the Database Management System maintain transaction time automatically, so that the integrity of the previous states of the database is preserved. To impart the bi-temporal solution in MS SQL SERVER, these are the following functions to be done:

- Creation of the Bi-temporal TABLE
- Normalization
- Insertion
- Updating
- Deletion
- Vertical and horizontal slicing (Selection and Projection) of bi-temporal data.

3.1 MODEL

EXTENDING DATABASE

The bi-temporal database modelling is an extension of temporal database which is already inbuilt in MS SQL Server 2016 onwards. The extending database should be predominant in bi-temporal nature. All the constraints and rules specified for temporal database can be incorporated into bi-temporal database. It's crucial to be known by the developers that focusing on bi-temporality helps in much deeper analysis for data interpretation and business requirements than the conventional relational database.

Here, in the data model, bi-temporal interactions and statements are explained. The essential difference comes down to storing the two time dimensions. [2] By extending non bi-temporal or temporal database it is possible to achieve bi-temporality in MS SQL server. Due to fact that most the database functionality can be reused, you only need to ensure data integrity and provide proper query language.

4 Bi-temporal Data Definition Language

4.1 BI-TEMPORAL TABLE CREATION

Due to the temporal upward-compatibility, temporal SQL queries returns the same results when executed on bi-temporal tables as if they were executed on non-temporal tables. The selection of valid data at time instant now in the tables referenced by the query and leaving away any timestamp attributes prior to further evaluation is firstly done. A bi-temporal table supports the tracking of a temporal table along with the time-specific data storage which is of an application specific temporal table. Use bi-temporal tables to stay user-based period information also as system-based historical information. Bi-temporal tables combines as system-period temporal tables and application-period temporal tables. All the restrictions that apply to system-period temporal tables and application temporal tables also apply to bi-temporal tables.

The constraints induced on instituting data into a database, altering data in a database, or removing data from a database, is such that the transformations should reflect what is happening to data that should be happened throughout the entire lifecycle. Thus, the syntax of those transformations maintain the semantics of the data. The constraints which every valid database state must develop to these such as entity integrity, referential integrity, domain integrity, and application-specific business rules, so that the data in the database is accurately and intelligently explain what it is about to those who manipulate the database.

Statement

```
CREATE TABLE table name
( ... NOT NULL PRIMARY KEY CLUSTERED,
// data
...Foreign ID type REFERENCES Parent table name,
[ RowEffective StartDate ] [ date time ] NULL,
[ RowEffectiveEndDate ] [ datetime ] NULL,
[ RowAssertionStartDate ] [ datetime ]
GENERATED ALWAYS AS ROW START,
[ RowAssertionEndDate ] [ datetime ]
GENERATED ALWAYS AS ROW END,
PERIOD FOR SYSTEM TIME
([RowAssertionStartDate], [RowAssertionEndDate] ) )
WITH (SYSTEM VERSIONING = ON
(HISTORY TABLE = dbo.tableNameHistory) ) ; [12]
```

Normalization

Bi-temporal approach requires a modern design modelling, than the traditional design called denormalization. Bi-temporal data has its own flaws in terms of complexity. The nature of bi-

temporal data causes issues that is specific to the modelling. Typical issues are redundancy, circumlocution, contradiction, homogeneity. As the answer, [1] 6NF allows attribute values to change independently of each other, thus avoiding redundancy and other anomalies. Independence can be maintained by incorporating irreducible components. When dealing with bi-temporal data, 6NF is a wise choice but complex in the application point of view. Or otherwise,

Time normalization

Time is distinct, and is calculated by a clock. At a certain point in time, two clocks can't be the same. For the time to be calculated in a database, a temporal database is required, which stores a collection of time-related data. Such a system eases storing, retrieving and updating historical and future data (generically referred as temporal data). Temporal data is data that changes over time. Valid time and transaction time can be supported in together and such a database is called a bi-temporal database, comparing to a non-temporal database. The temporal approach initiates additional complexities, such as schema of the model design and also the keys. It is useless if it cannot identify an application that does not evolve over time. This means that time-varying data is necessary. Built-in time management greatly increases the functionality of a database application. The database system thus maintains past, present, and future versions of data. A conventional database, without temporal property, has only the most recent data as storage. The old values are either replaced or deleted. The progress of real-world phenomena over time cannot be stored in the database as well as accessing past data is never considered as an option. Time values are linked with attributes that indicate their periods of validity. Precisely, the temporal theory usually include two types of time: valid and transaction time. Valid time is the time period during which a fact is true with reference to reality. Transaction time is the time when a fact is recorded in the database. The concept used in time normalization is the requirement that tuples are semantically independent of one another [3].

A relation is in time normal form (TNF) if and only if it is in Boyce-Codd-Normal Form and there exists no temporal dependencies among its non-key attributes. [3]

i.e., the attributes should be non-synchronous in time. If they are synchronous, decompose the table to produce the bi-temporality to each of the attribute.

5 Bi-temporal Data Manipulation Language

5.1 INSERTING DATA INTO A BI-TEMPORAL TABLE

It is same as the statement for inserting data into a temporal table.

Statement

```
INSERT INTO TABLE tablename  
VALUES (...);
```

//Avoid the columns of system generated transaction time values which will be automatically generated.

5.2 UPDATING DATA INTO A TABLE

Updating data in a bi-temporal table updates rows in history table and added to its current table.

Statement

```
UPDATE table name  
SET column name=' value '  
where key=' ';
```

The updating is in such a way that the data once inputted is never gone from the database and the data is coalesced and added to the history table along with current table.

5.3 DELETING DATA FROM A BI-TEMPORAL TABLE

Deleting data from a bi-temporal table deletes rows from the current table, and rows are added to its associated history table and which potentially result in new rows, inserted to the bi-temporal table.

Statement

```
DELETE from table WHERE...;
```

5.4 QUERYING BI-TEMPORAL DATA

Vertical and Horizontal Slicing i.e., querying a bi-temporal table can return results for a specified time period. These results consists current, historic, and future data.

A new clause FOR SYSTEM TIME in the SELECT ... FROM statement, which has five new sub clauses [10] to query bi-temporal table data:

- AS OF datetime
- ALL
- FROM start datetime TO end datetime
- BETWEEN start datetime AND end datetime
- CONTAINED IN (start datetime, end datetime)

SYSTEM TIME AS OF

The AS OF sub-clause returns rows from the bi-temporal and history table that are valid up to the time specified. It gives the complete snapshot of the current values until the specified time.

SYSTEM TIME ALL

ALL returns all the rows from the current and history table.

FROM and TO clause

The sub-clause FROM-TO returns results by combing the bi-temporal and history table because this clause excludes the upper boundary of the end time.

BETWEEN AND pair

The sub-clause BETWEEN-AND returns combined results from both the bi-temporal and history tables. This is because this sub-clause includes the upper boundary of the end time.

CONTAINED IN

This sub clause gives all rows from the history table included in the range specified. This is due to the command in the statement CONTAINED IN that returns data from the history table.

Statement

SELECT * FROM table name **FOR SYSTEM TIME ALL;**

// vertical slice

SELECT* FROM table name **WHERE**

//horizontal slice

SELECT * FROM table name
FOR SYSTEM TIME AS OF // specifying a date time – state of data
FROM TO // range – a data audit
BETWEEN AND // range – a data audit
CONTAINED IN (,) // range – a data audit
ALL // whole data

// vertical slice and horizontal slice i.e., bi-temporal slice

SELECT FROM table name
FOR SYSTEM TIME AS OF // specifying a date time – state of data
FROM TO // range – a data audit
BETWEEN AND // range – a data audit
CONTAINED IN (,) // range – a data audit
ALL // whole data
WHERE ...,

6 CONCLUSION

The data in engineering is so vast that the developers should be capable of handling data maturely. Enhanced versions of viewing and manipulating data is the need of the era. Just holding a data is meant to be of no use. Data that is meaningfully sorted is the core of an application. Time is the factor which produces meaning to the data. Thus, when we can add couple of entitlements to a single data automatically motivates enhancements in the server dimensionality.

Past historical data can always be a backbone of a business which is the complete decision maker and the game changer. Temporality in terms of data in the present time narrows the view of data. Enormous amount of data seen with past, present and future adds vital role to the business. The technologies used in medicine, law, education, etc., when shown with a meaning data brings a notion on the fact and predict the nature of the fact. There comes the importance of bi-temporal implementation of data. The structure, the normalization, the upward language compatibility is an essential backup solutions to the new implementation. In spite of that, the Bi-temporal implementation can be extended to more database types - relational, key-value stores, column value stores and document-oriented systems and graph systems. Bi-temporal operations, such as insertion, change, deletion and slicing can be implemented on multiple database management systems.

All core aspects of storing bi-temporal data in MS SQL Server is implemented and as more than a model it can be a great use case in analyzing data and report generation of business applications. This research tried to cover the bi-temporal DDL and DML operations in MS-

SQL Server.

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Track A: Security

Access control, Anonymity, Audit and audit reduction & Authentication and authorization, Applied cryptography, Cryptanalysis, Digital Signatures, Biometric security, Boundary control devices, Certification and accreditation, Cross-layer design for security, Security & Network Management, Data and system integrity, Database security, Defensive information warfare, Denial of service protection, Intrusion Detection, Anti-malware, Distributed systems security, Electronic commerce, E-mail security, Spam, Phishing, E-mail fraud, Virus, worms, Trojan Protection, Grid security, Information hiding and watermarking & Information survivability, Insider threat protection, Integrity
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Location Anonymity schemes, Intrusion detection and prevention techniques, Cryptography, encryption algorithms and Key management schemes, Secure routing schemes, Secure neighbor discovery and localization, Trust establishment and maintenance, Confidentiality and data integrity, Security architectures, deployments and solutions, Emerging threats to cloud-based services, Security model for new services, Cloud-aware web service security, Information hiding in Cloud Computing, Securing distributed data storage in cloud, Security, privacy and trust in mobile computing systems and applications, **Middleware security & Security features:** middleware software is an asset on its own and has to be protected, interaction between security-specific and other middleware features, e.g., context-awareness, **Middleware-level security monitoring and measurement:** metrics and mechanisms for quantification and evaluation of security enforced by the middleware, **Security co-design:** trade-off and co-design between application-based and middleware-based security, **Policy-based management:** innovative support for policy-based definition and enforcement of security concerns, **Identification and authentication mechanisms:** Means to capture application specific constraints in defining and enforcing access control rules, **Middleware-oriented security patterns:** identification of patterns for sound, reusable security, **Security in aspect-based middleware:** mechanisms for isolating and enforcing security aspects, **Security in agent-based platforms:** protection for mobile code and platforms, Smart Devices: Biometrics, National ID cards, Embedded Systems Security and TPMs, RFID Systems Security, Smart Card Security, Pervasive Systems: Digital Rights Management (DRM) in pervasive environments, Intrusion Detection and Information Filtering, Localization Systems Security (Tracking of People and Goods), Mobile Commerce Security, Privacy Enhancing Technologies, Security Protocols (for Identification and Authentication, Confidentiality and Privacy, and Integrity), Ubiquitous Networks: Ad Hoc Networks Security, Delay-Tolerant Network Security, Domestic Network Security, Peer-to-Peer Networks Security, Security Issues in Mobile and Ubiquitous Networks, Security of GSM/GPRS/UMTS Systems, Sensor Networks Security, Vehicular Network Security, Wireless Communication Security: Bluetooth, NFC, WiFi, WiMAX, WiMedia, others

This Track will emphasize the design, implementation, management and applications of computer communications, networks and services. Topics of mostly theoretical nature are also welcome, provided there is clear practical potential in applying the results of such work.

Track B: Computer Science

Broadband wireless technologies: LTE, WiMAX, WiRAN, HSDPA, HSUPA, Resource allocation and interference management, Quality of service and scheduling methods, Capacity planning and dimensioning, Cross-layer design and Physical layer based issue, Interworking architecture and interoperability, Relay assisted and cooperative communications, Location and provisioning and mobility management, Call admission and flow/congestion control, Performance optimization, Channel capacity modeling and analysis, Middleware Issues: Event-based, publish/subscribe, and message-oriented middleware, Reconfigurable, adaptable, and reflective middleware approaches, Middleware solutions for reliability, fault tolerance, and quality-of-service, Scalability of middleware, Context-aware middleware, Autonomic and self-managing middleware, Evaluation techniques for middleware solutions, Formal methods and tools for designing, verifying, and evaluating, middleware, Software engineering techniques for middleware, Service oriented middleware, Agent-based middleware, Security middleware, Network Applications: Network-based automation, Cloud applications, Ubiquitous and pervasive applications, Collaborative applications, RFID and sensor network applications, Mobile applications, Smart home applications, Infrastructure monitoring and control applications, Remote health monitoring, GPS and location-based applications, Networked vehicles applications, Alert applications, Embedded Computer System, Advanced Control Systems, and Intelligent Control : Advanced control and measurement, computer and microprocessor-based control, signal processing, estimation and identification techniques, application specific IC's, nonlinear and adaptive control, optimal and robot control, intelligent control, evolutionary computing, and intelligent systems, instrumentation subject to critical conditions, automotive, marine and aero-space control and all other control applications, Intelligent Control System, Wiring/Wireless Sensor, Signal Control System. Sensors, Actuators and Systems Integration : Intelligent sensors and actuators, multisensor fusion, sensor array and multi-channel processing, micro/nano technology, microsensors and microactuators, instrumentation electronics, MEMS and system integration, wireless sensor, Network Sensor, Hybrid

Sensor, Distributed Sensor Networks. Signal and Image Processing : Digital signal processing theory, methods, DSP implementation, speech processing, image and multidimensional signal processing, Image analysis and processing, Image and Multimedia applications, Real-time multimedia signal processing, Computer vision, Emerging signal processing areas, Remote Sensing, Signal processing in education. Industrial Informatics: Industrial applications of neural networks, fuzzy algorithms, Neuro-Fuzzy application, bioInformatics, real-time computer control, real-time information systems, human-machine interfaces, CAD/CAM/CAT/CIM, virtual reality, industrial communications, flexible manufacturing systems, industrial automated process, Data Storage Management, Harddisk control, Supply Chain Management, Logistics applications, Power plant automation, Drives automation. Information Technology, Management of Information System : Management information systems, Information Management, Nursing information management, Information System, Information Technology and their application, Data retrieval, Data Base Management, Decision analysis methods, Information processing, Operations research, E-Business, E-Commerce, E-Government, Computer Business, Security and risk management, Medical imaging, Biotechnology, Bio-Medicine, Computer-based information systems in health care, Changing Access to Patient Information, Healthcare Management Information Technology. Communication/Computer Network, Transportation Application : On-board diagnostics, Active safety systems, Communication systems, Wireless technology, Communication application, Navigation and Guidance, Vision-based applications, Speech interface, Sensor fusion, Networking theory and technologies, Transportation information, Autonomous vehicle, Vehicle application of affective computing, Advance Computing technology and their application : Broadband and intelligent networks, Data Mining, Data fusion, Computational intelligence, Information and data security, Information indexing and retrieval, Information processing, Information systems and applications, Internet applications and performances, Knowledge based systems, Knowledge management, Software Engineering, Decision making, Mobile networks and services, Network management and services, Neural Network, Fuzzy logics, Neuro-Fuzzy, Expert approaches, Innovation Technology and Management : Innovation and product development, Emerging advances in business and its applications, Creativity in Internet management and retailing, B2B and B2C management, Electronic transceiver device for Retail Marketing Industries, Facilities planning and management, Innovative pervasive computing applications, Programming paradigms for pervasive systems, Software evolution and maintenance in pervasive systems, Middleware services and agent technologies, Adaptive, autonomic and context-aware computing, Mobile/Wireless computing systems and services in pervasive computing, Energy-efficient and green pervasive computing, Communication architectures for pervasive computing, Ad hoc networks for pervasive communications, Pervasive opportunistic communications and applications, Enabling technologies for pervasive systems (e.g., wireless BAN, PAN), Positioning and tracking technologies, Sensors and RFID in pervasive systems, Multimodal sensing and context for pervasive applications, Pervasive sensing, perception and semantic interpretation, Smart devices and intelligent environments, Trust, security and privacy issues in pervasive systems, User interfaces and interaction models, Virtual immersive communications, Wearable computers, Standards and interfaces for pervasive computing environments, Social and economic models for pervasive systems, Active and Programmable Networks, Ad Hoc & Sensor Network, Congestion and/or Flow Control, Content Distribution, Grid Networking, High-speed Network Architectures, Internet Services and Applications, Optical Networks, Mobile and Wireless Networks, Network Modeling and Simulation, Multicast, Multimedia Communications, Network Control and Management, Network Protocols, Network Performance, Network Measurement, Peer to Peer and Overlay Networks, Quality of Service and Quality of Experience, Ubiquitous Networks, Crosscutting Themes – Internet Technologies, Infrastructure, Services and Applications; Open Source Tools, Open Models and Architectures; Security, Privacy and Trust; Navigation Systems, Location Based Services; Social Networks and Online Communities; ICT Convergence, Digital Economy and Digital Divide, Neural Networks, Pattern Recognition, Computer Vision, Advanced Computing Architectures and New Programming Models, Visualization and Virtual Reality as Applied to Computational Science, Computer Architecture and Embedded Systems, Technology in Education, Theoretical Computer Science, Computing Ethics, Computing Practices & Applications

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